

Technische Universität München

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Biotechnology of Horticultural Crops

Master thesis

Stereochemical structure-activity relationship of brassinazole, a potent inhibitor of brassinosteroid biosynthesis

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Date Submitted 30.01.2019

Acknowledgements

This research work would not have been possible without the support of many people. I express my heartfelt gratitude and sincere appreciation to my supervisor Dr. Wilfred Rozhon, Biotechnology of Horticultural Science, Technical University of Munich for his guidance, continuous encouragement and endless patience during the research work.

Special thanks to Prof. Dr. Brigitte Poppenberger-Sieberer, Biotechnology of Horticultural Science, Technical University of Munich for providing me the opportunity to conduct my Master's thesis in her research group and all the necessary facilities to attain this research work.

I am grateful to Assoc. Prof. Dr. Franz Berthiller for being my co-supervisor.

I would like to thank Dr. Pablo Albertos, Sufu Gan, Tanja Ibrom, Veronica Ramirez, Konstantin Wagner, Sebastian Schramm, Yuanyuan Liang and technical staff Irene Ziegler for creating a nice working environment in the lab and other necessary help during my research work.

Finally, I wish to thank to my beloved son Aareeb Rahman, husband Dr. Mohammad Asrafur Rahman, parents, other family members and friends for their endless support in every aspect of my life including this work.

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Abstract

Brassinosteroids (BRs) are a group of plant steroids with a wide range of biological activities such as promoting cell elongation and cell division and regulating flowering and senescence. Brassinazole (BRZ) is a potent triazole-type inhibitor of BR biosynthesis. In the framework of this study, BRZ was synthesised in a three-step synthesis. First, 1,2,4-triazole was reacted with phenacylbromide to 1-phenyl-2-(1*H*-1,2,4-triazole-1-yl)ethanone. Second, the product of step one was derivatised with 4-chlorobenzyl chloride. Third, the obtained product was reacted with the Grignard reagent methylmagnesium chloride to BRZ. Since BRZ contains two stereocenters, a mixture of the four stereoisomers was obtained. Analysis by HPLC revealed that the racemic diastereomers, which were named (±)-BRZ1 and (±)-BRZ2, were formed with different efficiencies: the obtained crude product consisted of approximately 70% (±)-BRZ1 and 10% (±)-BRZ2. In addition, it contained also approximately 10% educt that had not reacted and 10% of other by-products. (±)-BRZ1 could be obtained in pure form by crystallisation from 60% ethanol and subsequently from toluene. (±)-BRZ2 was obtained from the mother liquor of recrystallisation of the raw product from 60% ethanol by preparative HPLC using a Luna C18(2) column. Analysis by NMR spectroscopy revealed that (±)-BRZ1 is the racemic mixture of the (2*R*,3*S*) and (2*S*,3*R*) stereoisomers while (±)-BRZ2 represents the racemic mixture of the (2*R*,3*R*) and (2*S*,3*S*) stereoisomers. Subsequently, enantiomers were resolved by semi-preparative HPLC using a Chiralpak AD column. Using the enantiopure compounds, optical activities were measured by ORD and CD spectroscopy, which allowed assigning the signs. However, assigning the absolute configuration by comparison of measured and predicted CD spectra failed since CD spectra prediction by different DFT (density functional theory) software packages revealed contrasting results. Subsequently, the biological activities of the enantiopure compounds were assayed using *A. thaliana* Columbia-0 (Col-0) and *Lepidium sativum* (cress). The plants were grown on ½ MS medium containing different concentrations of the compounds under controlled conditions (for cress 21°C, 16 h light/8 h dark, 80 µmol.m⁻².s⁻¹ and for *A. thaliana* 21°C, 16 h light/8 h dark, 20 µmol.m⁻².s⁻¹) for 7 days. Afterwards, hypocotyl lengths were measured and the IC₅₀ values (concentration of the compound at 50% inhibitory effect) were calculated by logit regression analysis. The IC₅₀ results showed that (-)-BRZ1 had the highest activity with a value of 0.23 µM for cress and 0.053 µM for *A. thaliana*. (-)-BRZ2 was three times less active and the two remaining stereoisomers had an at least 7-fold lower activity. Since many triazoles impact on sterol biosynthesis, the impact of (-)-BRZ1, (+)-BRZ1, (-)-BRZ2 and (+)-BRZ2 on sterols composition of cress and *A. thaliana* was investigated by GC-MS analysis. The results showed that (-)-BRZ1, the most bioactive stereoisomer, and (+)-BRZ1 had no significant impact on sterol biosynthesis. In sharp contrast, (-)-BRZ2 and (+)-BRZ2 showed clear inhibition of sterol biosynthesis and thus these two stereoisomers lacked specificity. In conclusion, in the framework this study a method for synthesis of BRZ was applied and methods for separation of the diastereomers and enantiomers resolution were developed. Bioassays showed that (-)-BRZ1 is the most active stereoisomer and that it does not inhibit sterol biosynthesis, substantiating that it is a specific inhibitor of BR biosynthesis. In contrast, the other stereoisomers showed lower activity and, as an undesired side effect, inhibited sterol biosynthesis. BRZ has been

applied in more than 1000 studies in form of an undefined mixture of the stereoisomers. The data presented here show that preferentially enantiopure (-)-BRZ1 should be used for inhibition of BR biosynthesis to achieve maximal activity at minimal side effects. This study is the first attempt to correlate the stereo-chemical structure of BRZ with the biological activity.

1. Introduction

Plants produce a wide range of hormones including brassinosteroids (BRs), auxin, gibberellic acid (GA), jasmonate (JA), cytokinin (CT), ethylene (ET) and abscisic acid (ABA). The activities of these plant hormones are studied intensively to decipher their involvement in plant development and responses of plants to a broad range of biotic and abiotic stresses (Taiz and Zeiger, 2010; Bari and Jones, 2009). Compounds specifically inhibiting biosynthesis or signalling of plant hormones are invaluable tools for such studies. Brassinazole, a triazole-type inhibitor, is the most widely applied inhibitor of brassinosteroid biosynthesis, which has so far been used in more than 1000 published studies.

1.1 Brassinosteroids

Brassinosteroids (BRs) are a class of polyhydroxylated plant steroid hormones, discovered 40 years ago (Grove *et al.*, 1979). In plants and animals steroid hormones are key regulators of growth and development.

In animals, they function in a broad range of target tissues, including the male and female reproductive tracts, mammary glands and the skeletal and cardiovascular systems (Hall *et al.*, 2001; Wang *et al.*, 2002). BRs are perceived by a plasma membrane-localized receptor kinase (Wang *et al.*, 2001a).

In plants steroid hormones play a significant role in regulating growth and development (Oh *et al.*, 2012), including stem elongation, leaf bending, tracheary element differentiation and controlling several important agronomic traits, such as plant architecture, flowering time, yield and stress resistance including tolerance to salt, cold, drought and pathogens (Clouse and Sasse, 1998; Krisna, 2003; Vriet *et al.*, 2012). More than 70 BRs and metabolites have been isolated from plants (Bajguz, 2009). The biologically most active BR is brassinolide (BL) which was first isolated from pollen of *Brassica napus* in 1979 (Grove *et al.*, 1979).

1.2 Biosynthesis pathway

Brassinosteroids are derived from plant sterols. The biosynthesis pathway of BRs was initially elucidated by various labelled precursors of brassinolide (BL) (reviewed in Zhao and Li, 2012). Campesterol is the precursor of the BR biosynthetic pathway (Fujioka and Sakurai, 200). First, campesterol (CR) is converted to campestanol (CN) by C-22 oxidation and then BL is synthesised from CN through two parallel pathways which are the early and late C-6 oxidation pathway. In the early C-6 oxidation pathway, CN is converted to castasterone (CS) via six intermediates, which are 6 α -hydroxycampestanol (6-OHCN), 6-oxocampestanol (6-OxoCN), cathasterone (CT), teasterone (TE), 3-dehydroteasterone (3DT) and typhasterol (TY). Conversely, in the late C-6 oxidation pathway, CN is hydroxylated to CS via six intermediates, 6-deoxocathasterone (6-DeoxoCT), 6-deoxoteasterone (6-DeoxoTE), 3-dehydro-6-deoxoteasterone (3-Deoxo3DT), 6-deoxytyphasterol (6-DeoxoTY), 6-deoxocastasterone (6-DeoxoCS) and 6 α -hydroxycassterone (6-OHCS) (Suzuki *et al.*, 1994, Fujioka *et al.*, 1995 and Yokota *et al.*, 1990). Finally, CS is converted to BL (Figure 1).

Introduction

Figure 1: Biosynthesis pathway of Brassinosteroid and P450 enzymes

Many P450 enzymes including DWF4/CYP90B1, CPD/CYP90A1, ROT3/CYP90C1 and CYP90D1 are involved in the BR biosynthesis pathway. BR biosynthesis and the genes involved in that pathway have been revealed by identifying several BR-deficient *A. thaliana* mutants (reviewed in Asami *et al.*,

2000). Inhibitors targeting specific enzyme involved in BR biosynthesis can be used to control the BR levels in plant tissues (Yamada *et al.*, 2012).

1.3 Inhibitors

Inhibitors of BR biosynthesis are widely used to study the role of BRs in plant growth, development and to modulate the physiological functions and responses to environmental cues (Asami and Yoshida, 1999, Asami *et al.*, 2000). Many triazole compounds are known to inhibit cytochrome P450 enzymes, which catalyse oxidations (Rademacher, 1991; Testa and Jenner, 1981). Triazole derivatives can bind the iron atom of the haem prosthetic group of the P450s (Sekimata *et al.*, 2008) due to the built-in affinity of the nitrogen electron pair (Rogerson *et al.*, 1977). The selectivity for a specific CYP450 or a class of P450s is conferred by the structure of the triazole inhibitor.

1.3.1 Brassinazole (BRZ)

Brassinazole was the first triazole reported as a specific inhibitor in BR biosynthesis (Asami, 1999). It was derived by modifying the structures of the GA biosynthesis inhibitors paclobutrazol (PAC) and uniconazole (UCZ). These two compounds block sterol 14R-demethylation and reduce endogenous GA levels by inhibiting the P450 CYP701, which is involved in GA biosynthesis (Rademacher, 2000). It has been reported that UCZ decreases also the endogenous level of castasterone and inhibits BR-induced tracheary element differentiation (Yokota *et al.*, 1991). Brassinazole was first synthesised by Asami and co-workers (Asami *et al.*, 2001). BRZ has a tertiary hydroxy group, a triazole ring and two aromatic systems. It possesses two stereo centres (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Chemical structure of brassinazole

Therefore, BRZ exists in four stereoisomers (Figure 3). Investigation of the modes of action of brassinazole proved evidence that it inhibits the cytochrome P450 enzyme DWF4/CYP90B1 (Asami and Yoshida, 1999, Asami *et al.*, 2001).

Figure 3: Chemical structures of the four stereoisomers of brassinazole

1.3.2 Brz2001

An intensive structure-activity relationship study using BRZ as a starting compound led to the discovery of Brz2001 (Sekimata *et al.*, 2001 and Sekimata *et al.*, 2002). Based on comparison of responses of BRZ2001 and BRZ-treated cress to BL and GA₃ it was concluded that BRZ2001 might be more specific than BRZ (Sekimata *et al.*, 2001). The structure of Brz2001 is identical to that of BRZ except that the methyl group was replaced by an allyl group (Figure 4). Like BRZ, Brz2001 exists in four stereoisomers. The target site of this compound is DWF4 where it interacts with the heme iron of the CYP₄₅₀ monooxygenase (Takakusagi *et al.*, 2013).

Figure 4: Chemical structure of Brz2001

1.3.3 Propiconazole (PCZ)

A number of synthetic triazole derivatives have been developed for medicinal and agricultural purposes. These include fungicides and plant growth regulators. Propiconazole (PCZ) 1-[[2-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-4-propyl-1,3-dioxolan-2-yl]methyl]-1,2,4-triazole is a potent fungistatic applied against a broad range of phytopathogenic fungi. PCZ has a triazole ring, a 2,4-dichlorophenyl residue and a dioxolane ring with an aliphatic side chain. It possesses two chiral centres, C-2 and C-4 within the dioxolane ring (Figure 5). Therefore four stereoisomers exist (Figure 6).

In fungi, the mode of action of PCZ is inhibition of lanosterol 14R-demethylase (CYP51A1), which has a crucial role in fungal sterol biosynthesis (Yoshida and Aoyama 1991; Wiggins and Baldwin, 1984). PCZ can also inhibit CYP51 of *Candida albicans*, human (Warrilow *et al.*, 2013) and zebrafish (Morrison *et al.*, 2014).

Figure 5: Chemical structure of propiconazole

An effect of PCZ on BR biosynthesis was first reported in 2002 by showing its inhibitory effect on hypocotyl elongation of cress plants (Sekimata *et al.*, 2002b). However, at that time PCZ was concluded to be unspecific and was just used as a lead compound for development of Brz220 (see below). Nevertheless, Hartwig *et al.* described PCZ as a “potent and specific inhibitor of BR biosynthesis” in plants and suggested its use as an alternative inhibitor to BRZ and Brz2001, particularly for agricultural crops that often require large-scale applications (Hartwig *et al.*, 2012). Oh *et al.*, 2016 showed by using differential UV/VIS-spectra techniques that PCZ has a high binding affinity to CYP90D1, which catalyses C23 hydroxylation in BR biosynthesis.

Figure 6: Structure of the four stereoisomers of propiconazole

1.3.4 Brz220

Brz220 was identified as a potent inhibitor of BR biosynthesis by Sekimata *et al.*, (2002a). It has two asymmetric carbons (C-2 and C-4) and contains a triazole ring (Figure 7) that binds haem iron. It has four stereoisomers (Figure 8) with different biological activities.

Figure 7: Chemical structure of Brz220

Brz220 blocks the 22-hydroxylation step in BR biosynthesis as indicated by *in vitro* binding to recombinant DWF4 protein. Based on their cross hypocotyl elongation assays it was concluded that $(2S,4R)$ -BRZ220 and $(2S,4S)$ -BRZ220 showed the highest inhibitory activity. The two other stereoisomers, $(2R,4S)$ -BRZ220 and $(2R,4R)$ -BRZ220, were significantly less active. This indicated that particularly the S configuration on C-2 is crucial for its activity. IC_{50} and K_d values obtained by *Arabidopsis* hypocotyl elongation assays and *in vitro* DWF4 binding assays, respectively, of the four Brz220 stereoisomers are listed in Table 1.

Figure 8: Chemical structures of the four stereoisomers of Brz220

Table 1: The biological activity of four Brz220 stereoisomers

Compounds	IC ₅₀ (μM)	K _d (μM)
(2R,4S)-Brz220	6.95	5.71
(2S,4R)-Brz220	1.21	0.22
(2R,4R)-Brz220	18.7	6.05
(2S,4S)-Brz220	2.33	0.54

Data according to Sekimata *et al.*, 2008.

1.3.5 YCZ series

The YCZ series is based on the ketoconazole structure (Yamada *et al.*, 2012; Yamada *et al.*, 2013; Oh *et al.*, 2012; Oh *et al.*, 2015a). The YCZ series includes YCZ-14, YCZ-2013, and YCZ-18.

4-Chlorophenacyl bromide was used as the starting chemical to produce YCZ-14 ((2RS,4RS)-1-[2-(4-chlorophenyl)-4-[2-(2-trifluoromethoxyphenoxy)-ethyl]-1,3-dioxolan-2-yl-methyl]-1H-1,2,4-triazole) (Oh *et al.*, 2008). A previous study described that YCZ-14 is a potent inhibitor of BR biosynthesis. The structure-activity relationship of this compound has been studied in 2012, which showed the inhibitory potency is significantly affected by the type of the aromatic substituent (Yamada *et al.*, 2012).

Figure 9: Chemical structure of YCZ-14

The effort on the above study of YCZ-14 was limited to synthesis because of difficulty to separate chiral molecules and therefore a further study was carried out to reveal the stereochemical structure activity relationship of YCZ. To explore this, (2*RS*,4*RS*)-1-[[2-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-4-(2-(2-propenyloxy)phenoxy)methyl)-1,3-dioxolan-2-yl]methyl]-1*H*-1,2,4-triazole was chosen as a target compound which was named as YCZ-2013. The reason of this particular compound was based on data analysis of this compound in different literature which showed that the stereochemical properties of itraconazole share a common intermediates chemical structure with YCZ-2013 and from the previous study showed that an analogue with an allyloxy substitution exhibited an excellent inhibitory activity in BR biosynthesis (Yamada *et al.*, 2013; Oh *et al.*, 2013). The study of four stereoisomers (Figure 10) of YCZ-2013 (2*R*,4*S*-YCZ-2013; 2*S*,4*R*-YCZ-2013; 2*R*,4*R*-YCZ-2013 and 2*S*,4*S*-YCZ-2013) showed that 2*R*,4*S* and 2*S*,4*R* most potent in inhibiting stem elongation of *A. thaliana* plants in the dark (Oh *et al.*, 2013).

Figure 10: Chemical structures of four stereoisomers of YCZ-2013

Later on, another potent inhibitor was identified which was named as YCZ-18. In this study, to identify the target site, a step wise feeding experiment was conducted by using 6-deoxocathasterone(6-deoxoCT), cathasterone (CT) and teasterone (TE) to test which intermediate could rescue the YCZ-18-induced dwarfism of *Arabidopsis* grown in the dark. The result shows that TE reversed YCZ-18-induced dwarfism but CT did not reverse it. This result provides evidence that the target site of this inhibitor is C-23 hydroxylation of CT, which is performed by CYP90C1 and CYP90D1 (Oh *et al.*, 2015a). CYP90C1 and CYP90D1 are two closely related genes with redundant function (Ohnishi *et al.*, 2006). To determine the binding affinities these two proteins the corresponding genes were cloned into the pCold-GST expression vector to purify recombinant proteins. However, CYP90C1 could not be purified since it was little expressed and remained in the insoluble fraction. In contrast, CYP90D1 was successfully purified. The binding affinity of YCZ-18 to CYP90D1 was determined by measuring optical difference spectra (Oh *et al.*, 2015a).

Figure 11: Chemical structure of YCZ-18

1.3.6 Triadimefon

The triazole derivative triadimefon 1-(4-chlorophenoxy)-3,3-dimethyl-1-(1,2,4-triazol-1-yl)-2-butanone) is a P450 inhibitor widely used as fungicide, where it interferes with oxidative demethylation in sterol biosynthesis of fungi. In plants it was reported to block gibberellin (GA) biosynthesis (Buchenauer and Röhner, 1981). In addition, another study described that triadimefon shows a good binding affinity to DWF4 and thus inhibits also BR biosynthesis (Asami *et al.*, 2003). However, since it likely lacks specificity it is rarely used as a BR biosynthesis inhibitor.

Figure 12: Chemical structure of triadimefon

1.3.7 Fenarimol

Fenarimol (FM) is a pyrimidine-type fungicide. It is reported to inhibit C-14 demethylation in fungal biosynthesis of ergosterol (De Waard and Van Nistelrooy, 1980). It has one stereocenter. In dark condition, fenarimol induces dwarfism with open cotyledon of *A. thaliana* seedlings. A study carried by Wang *et al.*, (2001b) found that *A. thaliana* plants treated with FM showed shortened hypocotyl lengths in a dose dependant manner, indicating that it inhibits BR biosynthesis in plants. In line with these results, fenarimol was shown to bind recombinant protein CYP90D1, which indicates that it induced a typical type II binding spectrum in BR biosynthesis, with a dissociation constant K_d of approximately $0.79 \mu\text{M}$ (Oh *et al.*, 2015b). The chemical structure of fenarimol (Figure 13) is highly similar to α -(4-chlorophenyl)- α -phenyl-5-pyrimidine methanol DPPM4 (Figure 14), which is a potent inhibitor of stem elongation in cress in the light and for *Arabidopsis* in the dark. These results indicate that DMPP4 exhibited inhibitory activity towards BR biosynthesis. In addition, there is evidence that it might also partially inhibit GA biosynthesis (Wang *et al.*, 2001b).

Figure 13: Chemical structure of fenarimol

Figure 14: Chemical structure of DPPM4

1.3.8 Voriconazole

Voriconazole is used in medicine for treatment of fungal infections, particularly aspergillosis, histoplasmosis, penicilliosis and candidiasis. As a triazole fungicide, voriconazole comprises a 1,2,4-triazole ring. However, in addition it possesses also a pyrimidine ring. Like many other triazole fungicides, it contains a halogenated phenyl residue, an aliphatic side chain and a hydroxy group. From the four existing stereoisomers only the (2*R*,3*S*) form is used as a drug (Figure 15). Voriconazole belongs to the class of 14- α -demethylase inhibitors (Sanati *et al.*, 1997). Voriconazol has also been reported as a strong inhibitor of sterol biosynthesis in plants (Rozhon *et al.*, 2013). Cress and *A. thaliana* treated with voriconazole showed strong reduction of the hypocotyl length. Thus, it was initially speculated that it might inhibit either BR or GA biosynthesis. GA biosynthesis could be excluded as a target by feeding experiments, where GA could not rescue the stunted hypocotyl while treatment with 24-epi-brassinolide rescued the phenotype efficiently. However, subsequent analysis of the sterol profile suggested that voriconazole inhibits sterol synthesis, particularly CYP51, rather than BR biosynthesis. Interestingly, voriconazole inhibited cell elongation in many plants except strawberry. The resistance of strawberry was used to confirm the primary target in plants: CYP51 of strawberry was cloned and expression in the voriconazole-sensitive species *A. thaliana*. The transgenic plants showed significantly increased voriconazole resistance, substantiating that

voriconazole targets CYP51 rather than an enzyme involved in BR biosynthesis (Rozhon *et al.*, 2013). That raises also concerns about the specificity of many published inhibitors assumed to be specific for BR biosynthesis. While GA biosynthesis inhibitors can be identified by rescue experiments, differentiation of sterol and BR biosynthesis inhibitors is hardly possible at the phenotypic level. In contrast, determination of the sterol profile is required, which has, however, not been done for most compounds assumed to be specific BR biosynthesis inhibitors.

Figure 15: Chemical structure of voriconazole

1.4 Brassinosteroid signal transduction

The BR signal transduction pathway is important for the regulation of plant growth and development. BR signalling has been elucidated in the last two decades (Figure 16). Binding of BL to the extracellular part of the BRI1 receptor kinase promotes kinase activity of BRI1 which phosphorylates the negative regulator BKI1 on Y211. This releases BKI1 from the membrane and allows association of BRI1 with its co-receptor BKK1 or its two homologs, BKK1 and SERK1. Consequently, BAK1 and BRI1 trans-phosphorylate each other on specific residues. This enhances the signalling capacity of BRI1 and leads to phosphorylation of BSK1, which is released from the receptor complex. Phosphorylated BSK1 associates with and activates BSU1, which leads to dephosphorylation BIN2 kinase on Y200 turning it inactive. With the aid of PP2A, the unphosphorylated form of BZR1 and BES1 transcription factor can accumulate and bind to the promoters of BR-regulated target genes, which elicit plant growth and developmental responses such as cell elongation, leaf morphogenesis and flowering.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Synthesis of BRZ1 (-BRZ1 and +BRZ1)

The method of synthesis of BRZ was developed by Robert Vassallo in the framework of a research project report (unpublished). Here the procedure was slightly modified.

Reagents

1,2,4-Triazole, 2-bromoacetophenone, sodium hydride (60% suspension in mineral oil), acetone, toluene and heptane (water <0.001%) and methylmagnesium chloride solution 3 mol/l in tetrahydrofuran were purchased from Roth (St. Louis, MO, USA). Sulphuric acid (96-98%) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and diluted with water to a final concentration of 2 mol/l. *N,N*-Dimethylformamide (water <0.015%), water-free tetrahydrofuran (<0.003% water), ethanol (containing 1% 2-butanone, >0.5% water) and sodium sulphate were purchased from VWR Chemicals (Radnor, PA, USA). 4-Chlorobenzyl chloride was purchased from Alfa Aesar (Heysham, UK). Potassium carbonate was purchased from Roth (Karlsruhe, Germany).

2.1.1 Synthesis of 1-phenyl-2-(1*H*-1,2,4-triazol-1-yl)ethanone (P1)

A 250-ml two-neck round bottom flask equipped with a magnetic stirring bar (3 x 0.6 cm) was charged with 7.6 g (110 mmol, 1.1 equiv) 1,2,4-triazole and 120 ml acetone. The mixture was stirred until the 1,2,4-triazole had completely dissolved prior 20.4 g (150 mmol, 1.5 equivalent) finely powdered potassium carbonate was added. One neck was equipped with a 50 mL pressure-equalising addition funnel and the second neck with an internal thermometer. The flask was placed in a bath with ice cold water. The addition funnel was charged with 19.9 g (100 mmol, 1 equivalent) 2-bromoacetophenone dissolved in 30 ml acetone, which was added to the vigorously stirred reaction mixture within a period of 15 minutes, paying attention that the flask temperature stayed between 15 to 20°C. After addition was completed, the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for a further 2 h. The mixture was filtered using a Büchner funnel. The contents of the 250-ml round bottom flask and the filter cake were washed twice with 25 ml acetone. The combined filtrates were filtered through a folded filter into a 500-ml single neck round bottom flask and the solvent evaporated to dryness in the vacuum. Subsequently, 100 ml toluene was added, the neck was equipped with a 30 cm Dimroth-type water-cooled reflux condenser and the content refluxed until the solid had dissolved was only a small amount of brownish oil remained. Then the clear solution was poured into a 250 ml beaker. The beaker was immediately placed in a bath of ice cold water and vigorously stirred to enhance crystallisation and to prevent separation of the product as oil. As soon as crystallisation has started the beaker was removed from the water bath and allowed to cool slowly to room temperature. Crystallisation was completed by incubation at 0 to 5°C overnight. The yellow to orange precipitate was collected by filtration using a Büchner funnel, washed with 20 ml ice-cold (0°C) toluene and sucked as dry as possible. The crude product was re-suspended in 50 ml cold water (0 to 5°C) and stirred at 0 to 5°C for 1 h using a magnetic stirring bar. The mixture was filtered using a Büchner funnel and the solid washed with 20 ml ice-cold water, sucked as dry as possible and dried under

vacuum (2 mbar, 50°C) to yield 13.0-14.9 g yellow to orange product. The obtained product was recrystallised from 12.5 ml water per gram product. To enhance crystallisation the hot solution was transferred into a beaker placed in a cold water bath and stirred until crystallisation started. As soon as crystallisation had started the beaker was removed from the water bath and allowed to cool slowly to room temperature. Crystallisation was finalised at 0 to 5°C overnight. The mixture was filtered using a Büchner funnel, washed with 20 ml ice-cold (0°C) water and dried under vacuum (2 mbar, 50°C) to give 12.4-12.8 g of pale yellow crystals. Recrystallisation from 6 ml toluene per g product yielded 11.4-12.0 g (61-64%) white 1-phenyl-2-(1*H*-1,2,4-triazol-1-yl)ethanone.

2.1.2 Synthesis of (±)-(3*R*/3*S*)-3-(4-chlorophenyl)-1-phenyl-2-(1*H*-1,2,4-triazol-1-yl)propan-1-one (P2)

A 250-ml two-neck round bottom flask equipped with a magnetic stirring bar (3 x 0.6 cm) was charged with 100 ml heptane, 2.5 g sodium hydride as 60% mineral oil suspension corresponding to 1.5 g (62.5 mmol, 1.25 equivalent) pure sodium hydride and 10 ml *N,N*-dimethylformamide (Heptane was added to protect the reaction from oxygen and moisture and to remove mineral oil from sodium hydride). One neck was equipped with an internal thermometer and the second neck with a 50 ml pressure-equalising addition funnel. The flask was placed in an ice bath and cooled to 0 to 5°C. A solution of 9.35 g (50 mmol, 1 equivalent) 1-phenyl-2-(1*H*-1,2,4-triazol-1-yl)ethanone in 25 ml *N,N*-dimethylformamide was added dropwise to the gently stirred reaction mixture paying attention that the temperature remained between 0-7°C. The mixture was stirred for further 5 min prior dropwise addition of a solution of 8.85 g (50 mmol, 1 equivalent) 4-chlorobenzyl chloride in 6 ml *N,N*-dimethylformamide at a rate that the temperature remained below 7°C. After addition had been completed the reaction mixture was stirred at 0-7°C for 30 min and subsequently at room temperature for a further 60 min. Then the content of the flask was poured slowly into a vigorously stirred ice/water mixture (600 ml). Clumps were crushed using a spatula and the mixture acidified to pH 3 with sulphuric acid (2 mol/l). The precipitate was filtered using a Büchner funnel, washed with 100 ml cold water and subsequently with 100 ml heptane and sucked as dry as possible. The raw product was transferred to a 100 ml Erlenmeyer flask and dissolved in 50 ml tetrahydrofuran, 5g sodium sulphate was added and then the product was mixed with a magnetic stirrer for 15 min. The dissolved product was filtered using a folded filter paper. The flask and filter cake were washed with 5 ml tetrahydrofuran. Afterwards 400 ml heptane was slowly added to the combined clear organic extract. The mixture was incubated at 4°C overnight. The precipitate was filtered using a Büchner funnel, washed with 70-80 ml heptane and dried in the vacuum (2 mbar, 50°C) to give 9.5-9.7 g (61-62%) almost white 3-(4-chlorophenyl)-1-phenyl-2-(1*H*-1,2,4-triazol-1-yl)propan-1-one.

2.1.3 Synthesis and purification of (±)-(2*R*,3*S*/2*S*,3*R*)-4-(4-chlorophenyl)-2-phenyl-3-(1*H*-1,2,4-triazol-1-yl)butan-2-ol [(±)-BRZ1]

A 100-ml two neck round bottom flask was charged with 15 ml (45 mmol, 1.5 equivalent) methylmagnesium chloride (3 mol/l solution in tetrahydrofuran), equipped with a magnetic stirring bar (2 x 0.3 cm), one internal thermometer and a pressure equalising 50-ml dropping funnel and placed in

a bath with ice cold water. A solution of 9.35 g (30 mmol, 1 equivalent) 3-(4-chlorophenyl)-1-phenyl-2-(1*H*-1,2,4-triazol-1-yl)propan-1-one dissolved in 40 ml tetrahydrofuran was added drop wise at a rate that the temperature did not exceed 25°C. After addition was completed, the reaction mixture was stirred at 20-25°C for 1 h prior pouring it into 500 ml ice cold water containing 4 ml glacial acetic acid. The mixture was stirred for approximately 1 hour prior to filtration using a 7-cm Büchner funnel. The filter cake was washed three times with 30 ml water. The product was dried under vacuum (1 mbar, 50°C). HPLC analysis (see 2.3.1.) revealed that the raw product consisted mainly of three compounds:(±)-BRZ1 as main product, (±)-BRZ2 as by-product and P2 that had not reacted. To isolate pure (±)-BRZ1 the raw product was recrystallised from 60% ethanol (5 ml/g dried raw product) to give 6.4 g (65-66%) white solid. The mother liquor was kept for subsequent isolation of (±)-BRZ2 (see method 2.2). The white solid was recrystallised from toluene (3 ml/g dried product) to remove some a polar impurities. The weight of the pure product was 5.6 g (±)-BRZ1.

2.2. Purification of (±)-(2*R*,3*R*/2*S*,3*S*)-4-(4-Chlorophenyl)-2-phenyl-3-(1*H*-1,2,4-triazol-1-yl)butan-2-ol [(±)-BRZ2]

The mother liquor from re-crystallisation of raw (±)-BRZ1 from 60% ethanol contained approximately equal amounts of the starting compound 2, the main product (±)-BRZ1 and the by-product (±)-BRZ2 as revealed by analytical HPLC using a column Purospher STAR RP-18. The mother liquor was evaporated to dryness in the vacuum. The residue (1.2 g) was dissolved in 60 ml methanol and 3 ml 4M aqueous sodium hydroxide and 0.6 g hydroxylamine dissolved in 37 ml water was added. The mixture was kept at 50°C for 1 h and subsequently over night at room temperature (20-25°C). On the next day the mixture was filtered. The solid was discarded while the filtrate was set to pH 5 to 7 by addition of glacial acetic acid. The obtained solution was filtered through a nylon membrane with a pore size of 0.22 µm. The obtained solution was injected in aliquots of 7 ml (in total 14 injections) into a preparative LC-10A HPLC system (Shimadzu, Nakagyo-ku, Japan) consisting of a SCL-10Avp system controller, a LC-10AD pump equipped with a DGU-14A degasser and a FCV-10AL low pressure valve for eluent selection, a 7125 manual injector (Rheodyne, Rohnert Park, CA, USA) equipped with a 7 ml injection loop, a CTO-10AC column oven set to 25°C, a SPD-10Avp UV detector equipped with a 1 mm preparative cell and a FRC-10A fraction collector. A Luna C18(2) 5 µm, 100x21.2 mm column preceded by Security Guard C18 column (Phenomenex, Torrance, CA, USA). For elution 60% methanol (MeOH) was delivered at a flow rate of 2 ml/min for 70 min. Fractions were collected from 40 min to 70 min with 2 min (4 ml) for each fraction. The column was re-equilibrated by delivering 100% ACN for 15 min followed by 60% MeOH for 25 min (both at a flow rate of 2 ml/min) prior injection of the next aliquote. Presence of (±)-BRZ2 in the samples was detected by analytical HPLC using the conditions described in 2.3.1). The BRZ2-containing fractions (see Figure 19C) were pooled and evaporated in the vacuum (1 mbar final pressure). The analysis by HPLC revealed that the obtained product (440 mg) had a purity of approximately 94%. For further purification the product was dissolved in 35 ml 40% ACN and injected into the same preparative HPLC system used above, except that elution was performed with 40% ACN for 110 min and subsequently re-equilibrated with 100% for 15 min and 40% ACN for 25 min prior injection of the next sample. Fractions (2 min

corresponding to 4 ml) were collected from 80 to 120 min and presence of (±)-BRZ2 confirmed by analytical HPLC (see Figure 19F). Fractions containing (±)-BRZ2 were pooled and evaporated in the vacuum (1 mbar final pressure) to yield 330 mg of (±)-BRZ2.

2.3 Analysis of the compounds:

2.3.1 Analysis of purity by HPLC

For chromatography a LC-10 HPLC system (Shimadzu, Nakagyo-ku, Japan) consisting of a LC-10AT pump equipped with a DGU-14A degasser and a FCV-10AL low pressure valve for eluent selection, a SIL-10A autosampler, a CTO-10AC column oven, a SPD-10A UV detector and a SCL-10A system controller. The system was equipped with a Purospher STAR RP-18 (3 µm) with a dimension of 55x3 mm column (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) preceded by a 2 µm inline filter (VICI, Houston, TX, USA). The injection volume was set to 20 µl, the column oven to 25°C and the UV detector to 220 nm. As eluent 42% ACN (mixing 35.6% of 100% ACN and 64.4% of 10% ACN) was used at a flow rate of 0.5 ml/min. Analysis of one sample required 4 min.

2.3.2 Carbon, Hydrogen and Nitrogen (CHN) analysis

CHN analysis was performed with a Vario EL CHN elemental analyser (Elementar, Langensfeld, Germany) at the central laboratory of the Technical University of Munich.

2.3.3 Chlorine content

The chlorine content was quantified by the combustion method. The following steps were followed during this experiment:

- Standards were prepared according to the Table 2.
- An oxidative flask (Schöniger flask) was washed 3 times with distilled water and charged with 15 ml absorption solution (2 mM TRIS and 1 mM potassium bromide as internal standard).
- The flask was filled with oxygen by passing approximately 10 ml oxygen through the flask.
- Approximately 5 mg sample was weighted and folded with a 55 mm filter paper.
- The folded filter paper was fitted into the holder, lightened and immediately transferred into the oxygen flask, which was tightly sealed.
- After the sample had completely combusted the flask was shaken three times for 1 min with 2 min breaks in between.

Table 2: Standards for chlorine content determination

No	CI (µl)	Absorption solution (ml)
St 1	150	15
St 2	300	15
St 3	450	15
St 4	600	15
St 5	750	15
St 6	900	15

- Then the absorbed chloride was quantified by anion exchange chromatography. The system consisted of a P100 pump (Thermo Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA), a Midas autosampler (Spark Holland, Emmen, The Netherlands) and a Waters 430 conductivity detector (Waters, Milford, MA, USA). A Waters IC-Pak Anion HC 4.6 x 150 mm column held at 26°C in the column oven of the Midas autosampler was used for separation. The eluent (sodium gluconate 320 mg/l, boric acid 360 mg/l, disodium tetraborate 264 mg/l, glycerol 4 g/l, acetonitrile 12% and 1-butanol 2%) was delivered at a flow rate of 1.6 ml/min.

2.3.4 Infra Red (IR) spectroscopy

For IR spectroscopy KBr discs were prepared (2 mg compound, 200 mg potassium bromide) and the spectra were recorded with a 881 IR spectrophotometer (Perkin Elmer, Waltham, MA, USA).

2.3.5 NMR spectroscopy

NMR spectra were measured by Dr. Oliver Frank at the Chair of Prof. Dr. Thomas Hoffman, Food Chemistry and Molecular Sensory Science, Technical University of Munich. DMSO-d₆ was used as a solvent.

2.3.5 ORD and CD spectroscopy

Optical rotation was measured with a 341 polarimeter (Perkin Elmer) using a 10 cm cuvette and solutions of the compounds in methanol at the indicated concentrations (see Figure 24).

Circular dichroism spectra were measured with a J-715 circular dichroism spectrometer (Jasco, Tokyo, Japan) using a 1 mm quartz cuvette and 0.06 and 0.3 mM solutions of the compounds in ACN. The CD spectra were measured in collaboration with Dipl.-Ing. (FH) Walter Stelzer at the Chair of Prof. Dieter Langosch, Biopolymer Chemistry, Technical University of Munich.

2.4 Separation of enantiomers

Semi-preparative chiral chromatography was used for separation of the (±)-BRZ1 and (±)-BRZ2 enantiomers. The chromatographic conditions used for separation of (±)-BRZ1 and (±)-BRZ2 are as follows:

Table 3: Conditions used for enantiomers separation

Column	Chiralpak AD (Daicel) 00CE-BJ056 Dimension: 250 x 4.6 mm
Eluent for (±)-BRZ1	80% 2-propanol, 20% MeOH
Eluent for (±)-BRZ2	50% 2-propanol, 50% MeOH
Injection volume	200 µl
Concentration of sample	10 mg/ µl
Flow rate	0.6 ml/min
UV detection	220 nm

2.5 Analysis of enantiomer purity:

The same conditions were applied in HPLC except that 20 μ l of a solution with a concentration of 1 mg/ml were injected.

2.6 Hypocotyl elongation assay

2.6.1 Hypocotyl elongation assay with cress (*Lepidium sativum*)

In this study, garden cress (*Lepidium sativum* L. cv. Mega) was used which were purchased locally. Seeds were sterilized using the chlorine gas method (see below) and sown into 1000 ml glass jars containing 50 ml $\frac{1}{2}$ MS medium (Duchefa, Haarlem, The Netherlands) supplemented with sucrose 10 g/l and plant agar 8 g/l. The medium was autoclaved at 115°C for 15 min and cooled to 50°C prior addition of the compound to the indicated final concentration. Stock solutions were added according to appendices 7 to 12. DMSO was used as control. The jars were kept at 4°C for 1 day prior transfer into a BrightBoy incubator (CLF Plant Climatics, Wertingen, Germany) set to 21°C and long-day conditions (16 h light at 80 μ mol·m⁻²·s⁻¹ and 8 h dark) for 7 days. The hypocotyl length was measured with a ruler from 20 to 30 plants.

2.6.2 Chlorine gas method for seed sterilization

- 1) Seeds of *A. thaliana* Columbia-0 (Col-0) were filled into 2 ml reaction tubes and seeds of cress (approximately 2 mg seed) were transferred into 100 ml glass beaker.
- 2) The open reaction tube or glass beaker containing seeds was placed into a plastic box, which was placed in the fume hood.
- 3) 5 g sodium bromate was weighted and wrapped into filter paper.
- 4) A glass beaker containing approximately 40 ml 25% hydrochloric acid was placed in the box.
- 5) The sodium bromate wrapped in the filter paper was placed into the beaker containing the hydrochloric acid and the lid of the plastic box closed immediately.
- 6) The seeds were sterilized in the box for approximately 2-3 hours.
- 7) The lid of the box was opened in the fume hood and left open for approximately 10 min.
- 8) Seeds were used immediately for sowing.

2.6.3 Hypocotyl elongation assay with *A. thaliana*

In this study, *A. thaliana* Columbia (Col-0) was used. Seeds were sterilized using the chlorine gas method (see 2.6.2) and sown on 6 cm Petri dishes containing 10 ml $\frac{1}{2}$ MS medium supplemented with the compounds (see appendices 13 to 18). The Petri dishes were kept at 4°C for 1 day prior to transfer into the incubator and set to 21°C and long-day conditions (16 h light at 20 μ mol·m⁻²·s⁻¹ and 8 h dark). After 7 days micrographs (25x magnification) of the seedlings pictures were taken under a stereomicroscope (Olympus, Model SZX2-ILLT, Shinjuku, Japan) and the length of the hypocotyls was measured on the pictures using the 'Imaje J' software (Version 6, National Institute of Health, USA). The hypocotyl length was measured for 15-20 plants from each concentration.

Afterwards, IC₅₀ for each compound was calculated using a logit regression.

2.7 Western blot analysis

2.7.1 Plant growing condition of *A. thaliana* for Western blot analysis

A. thaliana expressing BES1-CFP under the 35S promoter (line 199-9 and 199-5) were used for western blot analysis. Seeds were sterilized using the chlorine gas method (mentioned on 2.6.2) sown on 6 cm Petri dishes containing 10 ml ½ MS medium supplemented with the inhibitors, if required (see Appendix 20). DMSO was used as control. All the Petri dishes were kept in 4°C for 1 day prior to transfer into the BrightBoy incubator (CLF Plant Climatics, Wertingen, Germany) and set to 21°C and long-day conditions (16 h light/8 h dark, 80 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$). Plants were grown for 2 weeks.

2.7.2 Sample preparation

- 1) Plants were harvested after two weeks and approximately 40-60 mg fresh plant material was transferred into a 2 ml safe-lock tube, placed two steel balls into the tube and ground for 2 minutes in a Recht mill at 60 Hz to a fine powder.
- 2) 4 times of sample amount of 1.33x loading buffer was added to plant material.
- 3) The tubes containing the plant materials and buffer were incubated at 95 °C and 800 rpm for 3 min.
- 4) Then the tubes were centrifuged at 13000 rpm for 2 min.

2.7.3 SDS-PAGE

- 1) Glass and alumina plates were cleaned and placed into the gel casting apparatus.
- 2) Glass plates and spacers were fixed.
- 3) The gel solution was prepared according to the table 4

Table 4: Components for SDS-PAGE (recipe for 1 gel with 1.5 mm spacer or 2 gels with 0.8 mm spacers)

Reagent	Separation gel 10%	Stacking gel
Buffer for a 10% gel	7.5 ml	-
Stacking gel buffer	-	2.2 ml
Acrylamide 40%	2.5 ml	0.3 ml
TEMED	10 μl	2.5 μl
APS 10%	100 μl	25 μl

- 4) A free space about 1 cm was left for the stacking gel.
- 5) The gel was covered immediately with approximately 300 μl 2-propanol and allowed to polymerise (approximately 10 minutes).
- 6) The 2-propanol was removed by washing with tap water.
- 7) The stacking gel solution was filled into the remaining space and the comb was inserted.
- 8) After 20 mins the comb was removed and slots were washed with tap water.
- 9) Then 5 μl of Page Ruler Protein Ladder marker and 10 μl samples were loaded into the slots of the gel and electrophoresed with 30 mA_{max} (for 1.5 mm spacers) and 200 V_{max} until the bromophenol blue front had migrated out of the gel.

10) The gel was used for western blot analysis.

2.7.4 Western blot

- 1) A piece of PVDF membrane was soaked for one second in methanol and transferred immediately to distilled water.
- 2) 6 pieces of 3MM filter paper soaked with 0.5x TBE were placed on a semi-dry blotting apparatus (PeqLab).
- 3) The membrane was placed on the filter papers and the gel was placed on the membrane avoiding any air bubbles.
- 4) Any area that was not used by the gel was covered with plastic foil.
- 5) Another 6 pieces of 3MM filter paper soaked with 0.5x TBE were placed on the gel and the lid of the semi-dry blotting apparatus was closed.
- 6) 100 mA (20 V_{max}) were applied for transfer overnight.
- 7) After finishing transfer the apparatus was opened and the gel removed from the membrane.
- 8) The membrane was blocked by incubation in blocking buffer at room temperature for at least 1 h.
- 9) The blocking buffer was replaced by a 1:5000 dilution of a GFP-HRP antibody (Milteny biotech, product number 120-002-105) in blocking buffer and incubated with gentle shaking at 50 rpm at 4°C overnight.
- 10) The membrane was washed 4 times with blocking buffer, 10 min for each step.
- 11) The membrane was washed 5 times with 1x TBS-T (10 min for each step).
- 12) The membrane was placed on 3MM paper to remove any buffer and subsequently placed upside down on 400 µl (10 µl per 1 cm² membrane) of substrate solution and incubated for one minute.
- 13) Any excessive substrate was removed and the membrane was placed between two sheets of clear plastic foil.
- 16) A film (Amersham HyperfilmTM ECL) was exposed to the membrane for 1 to 10 seconds and the film was then developed.

2.7.5 Coomassie stain

- 1) The SDS-PAGE obtained from membrane was covered with staining solution and incubated on a shaker at 40 rpm for approximately 5 min.
- 2) Then the staining solution was removed and the destaining solution was added. The destaining solution was changed several times until the background of the page became clear.
- 3) The page was transferred on a tissue paper and air dried for overnight.

2.7.6 Buffer and solutions used for western blot analysis

Blocking buffer: 1x TBS-T containing 5% milk powder.

Buffer for a 10% gel: 50 ml 1 M TRIS/HCL pH 8.8, 48.7 ml water, 1.35 ml 10% SDS.

Electrode buffer 10x: 144 g/l glycine, 30 g/l TRIS base, 10 g/l SDS sodium salt.

4x Loading buffer: 10 ml 1 M TRIS/HCL pH 6.8, 3.08 g dithiothreitol (DTT), 8% SDS, 40% glycerol, 0.05% bromophenol blue.

1 M TRIS/HCl pH 8.8: 30.3 g TRIS (base), 160 ml H₂O, 4M HCl to set pH to 8.8 and water added to total volume 250 ml.

1 M TRIS/HCl pH 6.8: 30.3 g TRIS (base), 160 ml H₂O, 10 ml of 37% HCl, 4M HCl to reach pH to 6.8 and water added to total volume 250 ml.

Staking gel buffer: 13.6 ml 1 M TRIS/HCL pH 6.8, 1.14 ml 10% SDS, 85.3 ml water.

1.33x loading buffer: 2.23 ml 4x loading buffer, 4.43 ml water.

25x TBS-T: 219.2 g NaCl, 1.25% Tween 20, 0.25 M TRIS/HCL pH 8.0.

Wash buffer: 20 ml 25x TBS-T, approximately 500 ml water.

Staining solution: 0.5 g Coomassie Brilliant Blue in 250 ml 2-propanol; 70 ml 100% acetic acid, 680 ml water.

Destaining solution: 150 ml 2-propanol, 70 ml 100% acetic acid, 780 ml water.

2.8 Sterol analysis by GC-MS

The protocol was adopted from a method developed by Tanja Ibrom.

2.8.1 Plant growing condition for cress

In this study, garden cress (*Lepidium sativum* L. cv. Mega) seeds were used. Seeds were sterilized using the chlorine gas method (see 2.6.2) and sown into 1000 ml glass jars containing 50 ml ½ MS liquid medium supplemented with the compounds. The medium was autoclaved at 115°C for 15 min and cooled to 50°C prior addition of the compound to the indicated final concentration. DMSO and voriconazole were used as controls. The stock solution (see Appendix 21) was added to ½ MS medium prior to sow seeds. Afterwards, all the jars were kept in 4°C for 1 day prior to transfer into the BrightBoy incubator (CLF Plant Climatics, Wertingen, Germany) and set to 21°C and long-day conditions (16 h light at 80 µmol·m⁻²·s⁻¹ and 8 h dark) for 7 days.

2.8.2 Plant growing condition for *A. thaliana*

A. thaliana Columbia (Col-0) was also used for sterol analysis. Seeds were sterilized using the chlorine gas method (see 2.6.2) and seeds were sown on 6 cm Petri dishes containing 10 ml ½ MS medium supplemented with the compounds (according to Appendix 22). DMSO was used as control. Afterwards, all the Petri dishes were kept in 4°C for 1 day prior to transfer into the BrightBoy incubator (CLF Plant Climatics, Wertingen, Germany) and set to 21°C and long-day conditions (16 h light/8 h dark, 80 µmol·m⁻²·s⁻¹) for 2 weeks.

2.8.3 Reagents

- 1) 1 M KOH in ethanol (0.56 g KOH in 10 ml solution).
- 2) Derivatisation reagent (500 µl MSTFA with 500 µl dioxan) [Note: MSTFA (*N*-methyl-*N*-(trimethylsilyl) trifluoroacetamide for GC derivatisation)].
- 3) Internal standard (IS) for *A. thaliana* and cress (5α-chlostan-3β-ol, 15 ng/µl; in dioxan).
- 4) Standard stock 1 for *A. thaliana* and cress (campesterol, 4.47 ng/µl; stigmasterol, 0.54 ng/µl; β-sitosterol, 50 ng/µl; in dioxan).

- 5) Standard stock 2 for *A. thaliana* and cress (brassicasterol, 0.50 ng/μl; cholesterol, 0.20 ng/μl; stigmasterol, 1 ng/μl; in dioxan).
- 6) Standard stock 3 for *A. thaliana* and cress (campesterol, 30 ng/μl; stigmasterol, 3.59 ng/μl; β-sitosterol, 60 ng/μl; in dioxan).
- 7) Standard stock 4 for *A. thaliana* and cress (brassicasterol, 2 ng/μl; cholesterol, 10 ng/μl; stigmasterol, 5 ng/μl; in dioxan).

2.8.4 Sample preparation for hydrolysis and extraction analysis

- 1) Approximately 25-35 mg fresh or -80°C frozen plant material and two steel balls were transferred into 2 ml safe-lock tubes and ground for 2 minutes in a Recht mill at 60 Hz to a fine powder.
- 2) 300 μl 1 M KOH in ethanol and 50 μl of internal standard (IS) were added to the samples. The samples containing KOH and IS were incubated at 60°C overnight.
- 3) Samples were removed from the incubator and allowed to cool to room temperature for 3-5 min.
- 4) 600 μl of H₂O and 500 μl heptane were added to the sample.
- 5) The mixture was shaken at 1400 rpm at room temperature in a Thermomix for 10-15 min.
- 6) The tubes were centrifuged at 13000 rpm for 5 min.
- 7) The upper organic phase (heptane phase) was transferred into a new 2 ml reaction tube.
- 8) 500 μl heptanes were added to the remaining aqueous phase and the mixture shaken for 10 min at 1400 rpm at room temperature using thermo-mixture.
- 9) The tubes were again centrifuged for 5 min at 13000 rpm.
- 10) The upper phase was transferred into the tube containing the first upper phase. The residue was discarded.
- 11) 800 μl H₂O was added into the tube containing the combined organic phases.
- 12) The mixture was incubated again at 1400 rpm at room temperature in a Thermomix for 10 min.
- 13) Then the tubes were centrifuged at 13000 rpm for 5 min.
- 14) The upper organic phase was transferred into a fresh 2 ml reaction tube and the lower phase was discarded.
- 15) One micro spatula (20 ng) of water free Na₂SO₄ was added into the tube containing the upper phase.

2.8.5 Solid phase extraction

- 1) A 100 mg Bond ELUT-CN-E column (Varian) was placed onto a SPE apparatus.
- 2) 1 ml dioxin and subsequently 2x 1 ml heptane were added into the column for equilibration.
- 3) The complete volume of the sample extract was loaded into the column (transfer any Na₂SO₄ was avoided) and allowed drop through the column by gravity.
- 4) 500 μl heptane was added into the column for washing and the column was dried by applying vacuum at 200 mbar for 30 s-1min.
- 5) A collection tube (2 ml safe-lock tube) was placed in the SPE apparatus for collection of the eluate.
- 6) 1 ml of dioxan was loaded into the column and vacuum (200 mbar) was applied for 30-60 s.

7) The tubes containing the eluate were evaporated in a SpeedVac (Final pressure was set to 1 mbar).

8) The evaporated samples were stored at -20°C until derivatisation.

2.8.6 Preparation of the standards

The following standards were prepared in 2 ml safe-lock tubes

Table 5: GC-MS Standards

No	Internal standard (IS) in µl	Standard 1 in µl	Standard 2 in µl	Standard 3 in µl	Standard 4 in µl
1	50	0	-	0	-
2	50	5	-	5	-
3	50	10	-	10	-
4	50	20	-	20	-
5	50	50	-	50	-
6	50	100	-	100	-
7	50	200	-	200	-
8	50	400	-	400	-
9	50	-	10	-	10
10	50	-	20	-	20
11	50	-	50	-	50
12	50	-	100	-	100
13	50	-	200	-	200
14	50	-	400	-	400

- All standards were evaporated in the SpeedVac (Final pressure was set to 1 mbar). The evaporated standards were stored at -20°C until derivatisation.

2.8.7 Derivatisation:

1) 50 µl derivatisation reagent (a mixture of equal volumes of MSTFA and dioxan) was added into each sample and standard. The tubes were closed and incubated at 60°C for 1 hour.

2) The solution was transferred into a ND9 autosampler vial containing a 50 µl insert. The lids were closed and the auto sampler tubes were placed in GC-MS auto sampler and analysis started.

2.8.8 GC-MS conditions

The following parameters were set for GC-MS analysis

Table 6: Autosampler conditions

Syringe size	10 µL
Injection Mode	Standard On Column
Injection volume	2 µl

Table 7: GC conditions

Column	Alient VF-5ms 30m x 0.25 mm x 0.25 µm (Order Number. CP8944)
Flow rate	1.5 ml/min
Injector	280 °C
GC: Carrier gas	Helium (He)

Table 8: Injector

Time [min]	Split state	Split ratio
Initial	on	10
0	off	off
1.5	on	60
6.00	on	10

Table 9: Oven, temperature programme

Time [min]	Temperature [°C]	[°C/min]
0	170	-
1.5	170	40
3.5	250	40
23.5	310	3
24.25	325	20
25	325	-

Table 10: MS conditions

Trap	220 °C
Manifold	50 °C
Transfer line	280 °C
m/z ratio	100-650
background m/z	180
Scan-time	14.5-20.5 min

- For evaluation, specific ions were selected (see Table 11; underlined m/z) and the area integrated for cholesterol, internal standard (IS), brassicasterol, campesterol, stigmasterol, β -sitosterol and sitostanol and total ion chromatograph (TIC) were measured for 14 α -methylfecosterol, 14 α -Methyl-24(24¹)-dihydrofecosterol and 14 α ,24¹-dimethylfecosterol no standards were available and thus their amount was estimated using the TIC according to He *et al.*, 2003.

Table 11: Retention time (RT) and masses

Analyt	RT	m/z
Cholesterol	16.6	329.8; 393.8; <u>368.8</u> ; 458.6
Internal standard	16.8	215.8; <u>355.9</u> ; 370.7; 445.6
Brassicalsterol	17.2	<u>380.8</u> ; 470.7
Campesterol	18.3	343.8; <u>382.8</u> ; 472.5
Stigmasterol	18.7	<u>394.8</u> ; 484.7
β -Sitosterol	19.8	<u>397.0</u> ; 486.5
Sitostanol	20.0	384.1; <u>474.0</u>
14 α methylfecosterol	18.5	379.9; 469.8
14 α -Methyl-24(24 ¹)-dihydrofecosterol	18.6	382.0; 471.5
14 α ,24 ¹ -dimethylfecosterol.	20.3	393.9; 483.8

- Afterwards, calibration functions were calculated in Excel.

3. Results

3.1 Synthesis of Brassinazole (BRZ1)

Synthesis of BRZ was adapted from a previously described three-step protocol (Min *et al.*, 1999). First, phenacyl bromide was reacted with 1,2,4-triazole in the presence of potassium carbonate at 20°C to form 1-phenyl-2-(1*H*-1,2,4-triazole-1-yl)ethanone (P1). Surprisingly, the raw product contained significant amounts (approximately 10-15%) of a by-product, presumably 1-phenyl-2-(4*H*-1,2,4-triazole-1-yl)ethanone, which was not mentioned in Min *et al.*, 1999. However, separation of the main and by-product could be achieved by recrystallisation from water.

Second, P1 was reacted with 4-chlorobenzyl chloride under strong alkaline conditions to form the next intermediate 3-(4-chlorophenyl)-1-phenyl-2-(1*H*-1,2,4-triazol-1-yl)propan-1-one (P2).

In the third step P2 was reacted with the Grignard reagent methylmagnesium chloride to yield the final product BRZ (P3).

Analysis of the crude product revealed that BRZ was present in two forms, the two diastereomers. The main product was called (±)-BRZ1 and the by-product (±)-BRZ2. Approximately 8-times more (±)-BRZ1 than (±)-BRZ2 were obtained. In addition, the raw product contained also significant amounts (approximately 10%) of P2. That might be explained by deprotonation of P2 and reaction with the Grignard reagent to a magnesium enolate that could not undergo a Grignard reaction. During sample clean up the enolate was hydrolysed and P2 obtained. Variation of the reaction (order of addition and speed of addition) had little effect on the ratio of P2 in the crude product. However, use of fresh methylmagnesium chloride was essential since with older batches a low yield of BRZ but a large fraction of P2 was obtained.

For purification (±)-BRZ1 was recrystallised from 60% ethanol, where (±)-BRZ1 was obtained as a white solid while (±)-BRZ2, together with P2 and some (±)-BRZ1, remained in the mother liquor. Since analysis by quantitative NMR and HPLC revealed presence of non-polar impurities (probably double benzylated derivatives obtained in the second step) the obtained white solid was further recrystallised from toluene. Finally, 5.93 g of white (±)-BRZ1 were obtained. Analysis by analytical HPLC confirmed that the obtained (±)-BRZ1 was pure (Figure 19A).

Figure 17: Synthesis of brassinazole (BRZ)

3.2 Purification of BRZ2:

The mother liquor from re-crystallisation of raw (\pm)-BRZ1 from 60% ethanol contained approximately equal amounts of the starting compound P2, the main product (\pm)-BRZ1 and the by-product (\pm)-BRZ2 as revealed by analytical HPLC (Figure 19B). Initial tests showed that (\pm)-BRZ2 can be purified by preparative HPLC with eluents consisting of either MeOH/H₂O = 60/40 or ACN/H₂O = 40/60. (\pm)-BRZ1 and (\pm)-BRZ2 were well separated with both eluents while separation of (\pm)-BRZ2 and P2 was better with 40% ACN than 60% MeOH. However, the crude by product was of limited solubility in 40% ACN while its solubility was much better in 60% MeOH. Thus, a methanol-containing eluent had to be used. In order to allow still acceptable separation of (\pm)-BRZ2 from P2 the later was derivatised to its oxime by adding hydroxylamine (Figure 18), which was less retained on the preparative C18 column. Thus, the mother liquor was evaporated in the vacuum and the residue (1.2 g) dissolved in 60 ml methanol and 3 ml 4M aqueous sodium hydroxide and 0.66 g hydroxylamine (dissolved in 37 ml of H₂O) was added. Afterwards, the mixture was incubated at $50^\circ C$ for 1 hour and subsequently overnight at room temperature (20 - $25^\circ C$), which converted P2 into its oxime (Figure 18).

Figure 18: Reaction of P2 with hydroxylamine

Afterwards, the mixture was separated by preparative HPLC using a column Luna C18(2). The fractions marked in Figure 19C in red were collected, pooled and evaporated. The yield was 440 mg.

Figure 19: Analysis of (±)-BRZ1 and purification of (±)-BRZ2. (A) Analysis of (±)-BRZ1 by analytical HPLC; (B) Analysis of mother liquor by analytical HPLC; (C) Purification of (±)-BRZ2 by preparative HPLC using 60% MeOH as eluent; (D) Analysis of the product obtained in (C); (E) Purification of (±)-BRZ2 using 60% ACN as eluent; (F) Analysis of the product obtained in (E). Conditions: Column used LichroCART 55*2 Purospher STAR RP-18 endcapped (3 μ m) for figure (A), (B), (D) and (F); eluent: 42% ACN, 220 UV detection; 0.5 ml/min flow rate; temperature 25°C; 150 bar pressure; injection volume 20 μ l. Conditions: Column used LUNA C18(2) 100 * 21.2 mm for figure (C) and (E); eluent: 60% MeOH for Figure (C) and 40% ACN eluent for Figure (E); UV detection 220 nm; flow rate 2 ml/min; temperature 25°C; injection volume 7 ml.

Analytical HPLC showed that the obtained (\pm)-BRZ2 was approximately 94% pure. The obtained (\pm)-BRZ2 contained some P2 which was the main impurities and also contained some trace amount of (\pm)-BRZ1 and P2 oxime (Figure 19D). For further purification the same column was used but elution was performed with 40% ACN. After separation of (\pm)-BRZ2 from the majority of the contaminants, the partially purified product was sufficiently soluble in 40% ACN to allow using it as eluent. Using that solvent system (\pm)-BRZ2 was separated completely from P2 and its oxime. The (\pm)-BRZ2-containing fractions (marked in red) (Figure 19E) were collected, pooled and evaporated in the vacuum. HPLC analysis showed that the obtained product was >99% pure (Figure 19F). The yield of pure (\pm)-BRZ2 was 330 mg.

3.3 Characterization of (\pm)-BRZ1 and (\pm)-BRZ2

The compounds were characterised by quantifying CHN analysis, quantification of the chlorine content, infrared (IR) spectroscopy and NMR spectroscopy.

3.3.1 Elemental analysis

The CHN analysis was performed at the central laboratory of the Technical University of Munich and the chlorine content was quantified by the combustion method and by ion exchange chromatography (carried out by myself). The results obtained are summarised in table 12, which shows that the measured and expected values are very similar.

Table 12: CHN analysis and chlorine content of (\pm)-BRZ1 and (\pm)-BRZ2

Element	Measured % (w/w)	Expected % (w/w)
C (\pm)-(BRZ1)	65.95	66.03
H (\pm)-(BRZ1)	5.53	5.54
N (\pm)-(BRZ1)	12.82	12.91
Cl (\pm)-(BRZ1)	10.82	10.98
C (\pm)-(BRZ2)	65.95	65.43
H (\pm)-(BRZ2)	5.53	5.58
N (\pm)-(BRZ2)	12.82	12.62
Cl (\pm)-(BRZ2)	10.72	10.82

Note: 2 replicated were performed for CHN analysis and 3 replicated were performed for chlorine content. CHN analysis and chlorine content of P2 is given in Appendix 1.

3.3.2 IR spectroscopy

The obtained infrared spectra of (\pm)-BRZ1 and (\pm)-BRZ2 in KBr discs are shown in figure 20A and 20B, respectively. The X axis and Y axis represent the wave number (in cm^{-1}) and transmission (in %), respectively. The broad absorption bands at approximately 3340 cm^{-1} originate from the hydroxy group. The sharp absorption bands at 3117 cm^{-1} and 3133 cm^{-1} of (\pm)-BRZ1 and (\pm)-BRZ2, respectively, originate from hydrogens bond to the triazole ring. Due to the presence of the C=N bond an unusually high frequency for C-H hydrogens is observed for the triazole ring. The bands at 3026

cm^{-1} to 3087 cm^{-1} and 1599 cm^{-1} to 1890 cm^{-1} and the band at 1489 cm^{-1} [(±)-BRZ1] or 1490 cm^{-1} [(±)-BRZ1] are indicative for aromatic systems. Such systems show usually also bands in the low frequent range of 700 cm^{-1} to 900 cm^{-1} . However, due to the presence of two aromatic rings and a triazole ring this region appears very complex and the bands at this low frequent region cannot be reliably assigned. The absorption bands slightly below 3000 are indicative for methyl (CH_3) and/or methylene (CH_2) groups. Both compounds show differences in the finger print region. However, it must be emphasised that (±)-BRZ1 is a solid while (±)-BRZ2 is a liquid. Since the aggregate state has a significant impact on the IR spectrum it is difficult to rate which absorption bands are indicative for (±)-BRZ1 and (±)-BRZ2. (Note: IR spectra of P1 and P2 are given in Appendix 23 and 24). In conclusion, the observed IR spectra are in agreement with the structures of the synthesised compounds.

Figure 20: Infra-red spectra measurement of (±)-BRZ1 (A) and (±)-BRZ2 (B). IR spectroscopies were recorded from KBr discs (2 mg compound, 200 mg potassium bromide) and the spectra were recorded with a Perkin Elmer 881 IR spectrophotometer.

3.3.3 NMR spectroscopy

The NMR spectra (measured by Dr. Oliver Frank at the chair of Prof. Dr. Thomas Hoffmann, Food Chemistry and Molecular Sensory Science, Technical University of Munich) of (±)-BRZ1 and (±)-BRZ2 are shown in figure 21. Both, the major and the by-product, showed highly similar NMR spectra, indicating that they represent diastereomers of brassinazole. Buschmann *et al.*, (1986) reported that the α -methyl group in RS/SR diastereomers of compounds similar to brassinazole shows typical proton chemical shifts in the range of 1.23 - 1.38 ppm and shifts in the range of 1.52 - 1.74 ppm for RR/SS diastereomers. The observed shift of the α -methyl group of the main product (±)-BRZ1 was 1.29 ppm, identifying it as the racemic mixture of the RS/SR forms (Figure 21A). The by-product (±)-BRZ2 showed a shift of 1.63 ppm, which is perfectly in the range expected for the RR/SS racemate (Figure 21B). In addition, Buschmann *et al.*, (1986) reported a high excess of the RS/SR over the RR/SS forms for similar reactions, which is in perfect agreement with the observations made here.

A.

B.

Figure 21: NMR spectra measurement of BRZ. (A) NMR spectra measurement of (±)-BRZ1 and **(B)** NMR spectra measurement of (±)-BRZ2. H and C-NMR spectra were recorded with an AV-500 NMR spectrometer. Note: NMR spectra were recorded by Dr. Oliver Frank at the department of Prof. Dr. Thomas Hoffman, Chair of Food Chemistry and Molecular Sensory Science, Technical University of Munich.

3.4 Enantiomer separation

In order to resolve the enantiomers of (±)-BRZ1 and (±)-BRZ2, semi-preparative chiral chromatography was applied. Initially, different columns and eluent systems were tested:

Using an Astec CHIROBIOTIC™ V column and 36% MeOH as eluent good separation of (±)-BRZ1 into its enantiomers was obtained. In contrast, (±)-BRZ2 did not resolve with this column and

MeOH/H₂O mixtures. However, a severe problem with that system was the very low solubility of (±)-BRZ1 in 36% MeOH. Thus, a maximum of only 50 µg of (±)-BRZ1 could be separated per run, which is too little to obtain sufficient amounts for further studies. However, that system is in principle suitable for analytical HPLC of (±)-BRZ1 while (±)-BRZ2 cannot be separated.

Next, a Chiralpak AS (Daicel) was tested with 2-propanol/heptane and 2-propanol/MeOH mixtures. However, no satisfying results could be obtained.

In contrast, excellent separation was possible with a Chiralpak AD (Daicel) column. Initially, different ratios of heptane and 2-propanol were applied. Best separation was obtained with pure 2-propanol, indicating that more polar conditions might be more suitable. Thus, mixtures of 2-propanol and MeOH were tested, which were indeed superior to 2-propanol/heptane systems of pure 2-propanol. Best results were obtained with 80% 2-propanol and 20% MeOH for separation of (±)-BRZ1 into its enantiomers and 50% 2-propanol and 50% MeOH for separation of (±)-BRZ2, as indicated in figure 22A and 22B, respectively. In both cases, it was possible to separate up to 2 mg racemic mixture per run (200 µl injection volume of a solution containing 10 mg/ml in the corresponding eluent).

Figure 22: Separation of enantiomers. (A) Separation of (-)-BRZ1 and (+)-BRZ1 and **(B)** Separation of (-)-BRZ2 and (+)-BRZ2. Conditions used: Column- Chiralpak AD (Daicel) 250 x 4.6 mm; flow rate 0.6 ml/min; UV detection 260 nm; eluent: 80% 2-propanol and 20% MeOH (Figure 20A); and eluent: 50% 2-propanol and 50% MeOH (Figure 20B).

Note: In figure 22A, the red line indicates the fraction of (-)-BRZ1 and blue line indicates the fraction of (+)-BRZ1 that were collected separately. The green line indicates the intermediate fraction, which was discarded. In Figure 22B, the colours have the same meaning except that the intermediate fraction was collected, evaporated, reconstituted and re-injected rather than discarded.

3.5 Purity of the enantiomers

The enantiomers (-)-BRZ1 and (+)-BRZ1; and (-)-BRZ2 and (+)-BRZ2 were analysed by analytical HPLC (Figure 23A-F) to analyse their purity. A solution of (±)-BRZ1 was injected as a control. The chromatogram shows that the racemic mixture was completely separated into the enantiomers (Figure 23A). Importantly, the purified enantiomers (-)-BRZ1 and (+)-BRZ1 were almost pure as only minute peaks of the other enantiomer was visible in the chromatograms (Figure 23C and E). Similar experiments were carried out for (±)-BRZ2. Figure 23B shows the chromatogram of the racemic

mixture of (\pm)-BRZ2, which was completely resolved into the enantiomers. Again, only minute peaks for the other enantiomer were seen (Figure 23D and F) Thus, pure enantiomers were also obtained for (\pm)-BRZ2.

Figure 23: Purity of (-)-BRZ1, (+)-BRZ1 and (-)-BRZ2, (+)-BRZ2. (A) Recemic mixture of (-)-BRZ1 and (+)-BRZ1; **(B)** Racemic mixture of (-)-BRZ2 and (+)-BRZ2; **(C)** Purified (+)-BRZ1; **(D)** Purified (+)-BRZ2; **(E)** Purified (-)-BRZ1; **(F)** Purified (-)-BRZ2. Conditions used: Chiralpak AD column (dimension 250 x 4.6 mm); injection volume: 25 μ l of a solution of 1 mg/ml; eluent for (-)-BRZ1 and (+)-BRZ1: 20% MeOH, 80% 2-propanol; eluent for (-)-BRZ2 and (+)-BRZ2: 50% MeOH, 50% 2-propanol.

3.6 Optical activity of the enantiomers

3.6.1 Optical Rotation Dispersion (ORD)

The pure compounds (-)-BRZ1, (+)-BRZ1, (-)-BRZ2, (+)-BRZ2 were used to measure the optical activities of the stereoisomers (Figure 24). The (-)-BRZ1 and (+)-BRZ1 showed lower optical activities than (-)-BRZ2 and (+)-BRZ2. As expected, the optical activity of (-)-BRZ1 and (+)-BRZ1 was similar but the signs were different. Similarly, the optical activity of (-)-BRZ2 and (+)-BRZ2 was similar but the signs were opposite. This results confirm that (-)-BRZ1 and (+)-BRZ1 as well as (-)-BRZ2 and (+)-BRZ2 are enantiomers.

Figure 24: ORD curve of (-)-BRZ1, (+)-BRZ1 and (-)-BRZ2, (+)-BRZ2 stereoisomers. Optical rotation was measured with a 341 polarimeter (Perkin Elmer) using a 10 cm cuvette and solutions of the compounds in methanol at the following concentrations: 5.31 g/l for (+)-BRZ1; 5.10 g/l for (-)-BRZ1; 6.50 g/l for (+)-BRZ2 and 7.27 g/l for (-)-BRZ2.

3.6.2 CD (Circular dichroism) Spectra of BRZ stereoisomers

CD spectra show the differential absorption of the left and right polarized light of the enantiomers. Theoretically it is possible to determine the absolute configuration of a compound by comparing its CD measured spectrum with a CD spectrum predicted by the density functional theory (DFT). The measured CD spectra of (-)-BRZ1, (+)-BRZ1 and (-)-BRZ2, (+)-BRZ2 are shown in Figure 25. Acetonitrile was used as a solvent since it does not form hydrogen bonds with the compounds, which was thought to simplify DFT calculations.

A.

Figure 25: CD spectra of (-)-BRZ1, (+)-BRZ1 and (-)-BRZ2, (+)-BRZ2. Circular dichroism spectra were measured with a J-715 circular dichroism spectrometer (Jasco, Tokyo, Japan) using 0.06 mM solution of the compounds in ACN. Note: The CD spectra were recorded in collaboration with Dipl.-

Ing. (FH) Walter Stelzer at the Chair of Prof. Dieter Langosch, Biopolymer Chemistry, Technical University of Munich.

DFT calculations were carried out by Sarah Schmitz, at the Department of Theoretical Chemistry, University of Bonn, Germany. The green and blue line shown in Figure 25 displays spectra of (-)-BRZ1 calculated by two different methods. The dotted line represents the measured CD spectrum of (-)-BRZ1. As is shown in figure. 26, the CD spectra predicted by different DFT (density functional theory) software packages resulted in opposing results and none fitted the measured spectrum very well. Thus, the approach to identify the absolute configuration of the enantiomers by comparing calculated and measured CD spectra failed.

B.

Figure 26: Identification of the absolute configuration of (-)-BRZ1 by CD spectrum. The data for the measured CD spectrum were taken from Figure 25 (dotted line). The predictions for the CD (blue and green line) were calculated by Sarah Schmitz, Department of Theoretical Chemistry, University of Bonn, Germany.

3.7 Biological activity of BRZ and its enantiomers

3.7.1 IC₅₀ evaluation

A. thaliana is an excellent model system for research on plant hormone biosynthesis, signalling pathway, identifying genes, determining their functions and genome analysis because of its short generation, large number of offspring, small size and small diploid nuclear genome (Santner and Estelle, 2009; Meinke *et al.*, 1998). Similarly, cress plant is highly suitable for stem elongation test because it reacts sensitively to brassinosteroid deficiency (Min *et. al.*, 1999). Thus, to compare the biological activities of the purified compounds the widely used cress hypocotyl elongation system was used. In addition, the activities of the purified enantiomers were also measured using *A. thaliana* hypocotyl elongation growth assays since this plant species is an important model system. For

comparison the IC_{50} values, meaning the inhibitor concentration at 50% maximal response are reported.

3.7.1.1 IC_{50} (in $\mu\text{mol/l}$) evaluation for cress hypocotyl elongation assays

As expected, the hypocotyl length was reduced with increasing concentrations of the compounds. However, at very low concentrations no effect was observed and maximal hypocotyl length was observed. Typical results are shown in Figure 27 (A-F). With increasing concentrations the hypocotyl length decreased until it reached its minimum. From that point on a further increase of the inhibitor had little effect. Thus, the half maximal response was defined as the average of minimal and maximal hypocotyl length and the IC_{50} as concentration at half maximal response. In order to calculate these parameters a logit regression was used as previously described for analysis of the IC_{50} of bikinin-type inhibitors (Rozhon *et al.*, 2014). The IC_{50} value of each compound was measured at least three times for calculation of the average and SD. As indicated in Table 13, (-)-BRZ1 was the by far most active compound with an IC_{50} as low as $0.23 \pm 0.05 \mu\text{mol/l}$. Its enantiomer, (+)-BRZ1, showed with an IC_{50} of $2.70 \pm 0.37 \mu\text{mol/l}$ a 10-fold lower activity. The racemic mixture (\pm)-BRZ1 had, as expected, approximately half the activity of (-)-BRZ1.

Also the diastereomer (\pm)-BRZ2 had comparatively little activity. (-)-BRZ2 had with an IC_{50} of $0.89 \pm 0.31 \mu\text{mol/l}$ only approximately $\frac{1}{4}$ of the activity of (-)-BRZ1. The activity of (+)-BRZ2 was similar to that of (+)-BRZ1 and thus approximately 10-times lower than that of the most active stereoisomer (-)-BRZ1.

Voriconazole, an inhibitor of sterol biosynthesis, was also very potent in reducing the hypocotyl length. Voriconazole was included in this experiment since it was needed as a reference for analysis of the sterol composition by GC-MS.

A.

B.

Figure 27: The relationship of cress hypocotyls length (in cm) and different concentration (in $\mu\text{mol/l}$) of BRZ compounds. Plants were grown in 21°C under long-day conditions (16 h light at $80 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ and 8 h dark) for 7 days. **(A)** (-)-BRZ1 (experiment 2). **(B)** (-)-BRZ2 (experiment 2). **(C)** (+)-BRZ1 (experiment 3). **(D)** (+)-BRZ2 (experiment 1). **(E)** (\pm)-BRZ1 (experiment 1). **(F)** (\pm)-BRZ2 (experiment 1). Note: The value for the control ($0 \mu\text{mol/l}$) was mathematically treated as $10^{-100} \mu\text{mol/l}$. Diagrams for replications are given in the appendix 25, 26, 27, 28, 29 and 30.

Table 13: IC_{50} (in $\mu\text{mol/l}$) values obtained for cress hypocotyls length of (\pm)-BRZ1, (-)-BRZ1, (+)-BRZ1, (\pm)-BRZ2, (-)-BRZ2, (+)-BRZ2 and voriconazole

Compound	Average $\mu\text{mol/l}$	SD $\mu\text{mol/l}$	SD in %	Replicates
(\pm)-BRZ1	0.371	0.136	36.6	7
(-)-BRZ1	0.233	0.052	22.4	3
(+)-BRZ1	2.703	0.368	13.6	3
(\pm)-BRZ2	1.087	0.354	32.6	3
(-)-BRZ2	0.890	0.313	35.2	3
(+)-BRZ2	2.822	0.414	14.7	3
Voriconazole ^a	0.083	0.119	22.9	3

^a IC_{50} experiments of Voriconazole were carried out by Natalie Kraus.

3.7.1.2 IC₅₀ (in µmol/l) evaluation for *A. thaliana* elongation assays

In addition to cress, also *A. thaliana* was used for IC₅₀ experiments since it is one of the most important plant model systems. The results obtained using *A. thaliana* (Figure 28) showed a similar trend as that obtained with cress. However, the values were in general approximately 2 to 3-fold lower than with cress. That might be explained by the much shorter hypocotyl of *A. thaliana* than of cress. Consequently, in *A. thaliana* the distance for transport is much shorter and higher concentration *in planta* might be reached.

Again, (-)-BRZ1 was with an IC₅₀ of 0.044 µmol/l the most active stereoisomer. (-)-BRZ2 was with an IC₅₀ of 0.17 µmol/l 3-times less active. The two remaining stereoisomers, (+)-BRZ1 and (+)-BRZ2 showed an IC₅₀ of 0.84 µmol/l and 1.46 µmol/l, respectively, and therefore comparatively little activity. Taken these data together, (-)-BRZ1 is the most bioactive BRZ stereoisomer.

Figure 28: The relationship between *A. thaliana* hypocotyls length (in mm) and different concentrations (in µmol/l) of BRZ compounds. Plants were grown in 21°C under long-day conditions (16 h light at 20 µmol·m⁻²·s⁻¹ and 8 h dark) for 7 days. **(A)** (-)-BRZ1 (experiment 2). **(B)** (-)-BRZ2 (experiment 1), **(C)** (+)-BRZ1 (experiment 3). **(D)** (+)-BRZ2 (experiment 1). Replications are shown in Appendix 31, 32, 33 and 34.

Table 14: IC₅₀ (in $\mu\text{mol/l}$) values obtained for *A. thaliana* hypocotyls length of (-)-BRZ1, (+)-BRZ1, (-)-BRZ2 and (+)-BRZ2

Compound	Average $\mu\text{mol/l}$	SD $\mu\text{mol/l}$	SD in %	Replicates
(-)-BRZ1	0.053	0.009	17.6	3
(+)-BRZ1	0.728	0.208	28.6	3
(-)-BRZ2	0.178	0.033	18.3	3
(+)-BRZ2	1.106	0.364	32.9	3

3.7.2 Western Blot Analysis

Biochemical studies revealed that the phosphorylation patterns of BZR1 (Brassinosteroid Intensive 1) and BES1/BZR2 (Brassinosteroid Intensive 2), two transcription factors regulating BR responsive genes, are regulated by BR signalling. Thus, the phosphorylation pattern of these proteins can be used for assessing the activity of BR signalling (Yamada *et al.*, 2013).

In this study, *A. thaliana* BES1-CFP plants were treated with the BRZ stereoisomers and afterwards the protein phosphorylation pattern of BES1 was analysed by Western Blot analysis.

Staining with Coomassie Brilliant blue R250 showed that equal protein amounts were loaded on the SDS gel (Figure 29). The Western blot showed two bands for BES1: the intense upper band represents the phosphorylated form while the lower faint band is dephosphorylated BES1 (Figure 30). However, blocking BR biosynthesis by the tested BRZ stereoisomers had no clear effect on the observed pattern. This is not very surprising since the major fraction of BES1-CFP was already phosphorylated in untreated plants. Thus, it is hardly possible to detect further BES1 phosphorylation using that system. Thus, this experiment does, due to these technical limitations, not allow drawing any conclusions about the biological activities of the tested stereoisomers.

Figure 29: Staining with Coomassie Brilliant blue R250 expressing equal amount of BES1-CFP plants protein.

Figure 30: BES1-phosphorylation and BES1 pattern in the membrane developed in film of Western blot analysis.

Legends of figure 29: Lane 1 represents the protein marker; lane 2: protein of DMSO/Control; lane 3: protein of the plants that were treated with (-)-BRZ1 of 0.5 μM ; lane 4: protein of the plants that were treated with (-)-BRZ1 of 1 μM ; lane 5: protein obtained from that plants which were treated with (+)-BRZ1 of 0.5 μM ; lane 6: protein of the plants that were treated with (+)-BRZ1 of 1 μM ; lane 7: protein of the plants that were treated with (-)-BRZ2 of 0.5 μM ; lane 8: protein of the plants that were treated with (-)-BRZ2 of 1 μM ; lane 9: protein obtained from the plants, treated with(+)-BRZ2 of 0.5 μM and lane 10: represents the protein that obtained from (+)-BRZ2 of 1 μM treated plants.

Legends of figure 30: Lane 1: DMSO/Control; lane 2: plants treated with (-)-BRZ1 of 0.5 μM ; lane 3: plants treated with (-)-BRZ1 of 1 μM ; lane 4: plants which were treated with (+)-BRZ1 of 0.5 μM ; lane 5: plants that were treated with (+)-BRZ1 of 1 μM ; lane 6: plants treated with (-)-BRZ2 of 0.5 μM ; lane 7: plants treated with (-)-BRZ2 of 1 μM ; lane 8: plants, treated with(+)-BRZ2 of 0.5 μM and lane 9: plants treated with (+)-BRZ2 of 1 μM .

Note: *A. thaliana* BES1-CFP plants were grown in 21°C under long-day conditions (16 h light at 80 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ and 8 h dark) for 2 weeks.

3.7.3 Sterol composition of the plants by GC-MS analysis

Plant sterols are derived from cycloartenol through a series of demethylations, reductions, isomerisations and desaturations. Plants contain a mixture of sterols including stigmasterol, sitosterol, campesterol, brassicasterol and cholesterol (Sitbon and Jonsson, 2001). Many triazole compounds are known to inhibit sterol biosynthesis in fungi, yeasts and animals.

To investigate whether (-)-BRZ1, (+)-BRZ1, (-)-BRZ2 and (+)-BRZ2 have any impact on the sterols composition cress and *A. thaliana* plants treated with these compounds were analysed by GC-MS. As control plants treated with DMSO (negative control) and voriconazole as a positive control for a compound inhibiting sterol biosynthesis were analysed. The later compound was only applied in cress since no IC_{50} values were available for voriconazole in *A. thaliana*. To compare side effects at a given potency of the inhibitor it was decided to use the 1-fold IC_{50} concentration for each inhibitor. In addition, to test also a higher concentration, a treatment with the 3-fold IC_{50} concentration was included as well.

3.7.3.1 Quantification of sterol in cress

In cress, β -sitosterol, campesterol, stigmasterol, sitostanol, cholesterol, 14 α -methylfecosterol and 14 α ,24¹-dimethylfecosterol could be detected and quantified by GC-MS.

(-)-BRZ1 had no impact on the bulk sterols β -sitosterol, campesterol and stigmasterol (Figure 31A-C). A slight effect at the border of significance was observed for sitostanol and cholesterol (Figure 31D and 31E). Unusual sterols like 14 α -methylfecosterol and 14 α ,24¹-dimethylfecosterol (Figure 31F and 31G) typical for compounds targeting CYP51 (see results for voriconazole) were not observed for (-)-BRZ1. These data show that (-)-BRZ1 does not impact significantly on sterol biosynthesis.

(+)-BRZ1 showed almost identical result as (-)-BRZ1. The β -sitosterol content in plants treated with 1x the IC_{50} concentration of (+)-BRZ1 was not altered. At 3x the IC_{50} concentration a seemingly significant but small increase of the β -sitosterol content was observed (p value 0.004). However, it

must be emphasised that the SD for β -sitosterol of that sample was by chance very small; consequently, the significance of this result is questionable. Nevertheless, this enantiomer has no impact on the campesterol and cholesterol content and also 14α -methylfecosterol and $14\alpha,24^1$ -dimethylfecosterol could not be detected. This indicates that (+)-BRZ1 has no undesired side effect as inhibitor of sterol biosynthesis.

Plants treated with 1x and 3x (-)-BRZ2 demonstrated that this compound had a significant impact ($p=0.023$ and 0.008 respectively) on β -sitosterol and campesterol ($p=0.009$ and 0.001) contents. For stigmasterol, sitostanol, 14α -methylfecosterol and $14\alpha,24^1$ -dimethylfecosterol content a highly significant effect was observed for plants treated with 3x the IC_{50} concentration of this inhibitor. Similar results were also observed for (+)-BRZ2 and, importantly, for voriconazole, a known sterol biosynthesis inhibitor (Rozhon *et al.*, 2013). These data show that both BRZ2 enantiomers have undesired side effects on sterol biosynthesis. Thus, presence of these stereoisomers must be strictly avoided if BRZ shall be used as a BR biosynthesis inhibitor.

A.

B.

C.

D.

Figure 31: Sterol content in BRZ treated cress plants. Plants were grown in 21°C under long-day conditions (16 h light at $80 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ and 8 h dark) for 7 days **(A)** campesterol content in 1 week old cress plants treated with 1x and 3x of IC_{50} of (-)-BRZ1, (+)-BRZ1, (-)-BRZ2, (+)-BRZ2, and voriconazole; **(B)** Content of β -sitosterol in (-)-BRZ1, (+)-BRZ1, (-)-BRZ2, (+)-BRZ2, and voriconazole treated 1 week old cress plants treated with 1x and 3x of IC_{50} ; **(C)** stigmasterol content in (-)-BRZ1, (+)-BRZ1, (-)-BRZ2, (+)-BRZ2, and voriconazole treated 1 week old cress plants treated with 1x and 3x of IC_{50} ; **(D)** sitostanol content in 1 week old cress plants treated with 1x and 3x of IC_{50} of (-)-BRZ1, (+)-BRZ1, (-)-BRZ2, (+)-BRZ2, and voriconazole; **(E)** cholesterol content in 1 week old cress plants treated with 1x and 3x of IC_{50} of (-)-BRZ1, (+)-BRZ1, (-)-BRZ2, (+)-BRZ2, and voriconazole; **(F)** 14 α -Methylfecosterol content in 1 week old cress plants treated with 1x and 3x of IC_{50} of (-)-BRZ1, (+)-BRZ1, (-)-BRZ2, (+)-BRZ2, and voriconazole; **(G)** 14 α ,24¹-Dimethylfecosterol content in 1 week old cress plants treated with 1x and 3x of IC_{50} of (-)-BRZ1, (+)-BRZ1, (-)-BRZ2, (+)-BRZ2, and voriconazole. Note: control (ctrl) plants were treated with DMSO. The error bars represent the SD.

3.7.3.2 Quantification of sterol in *A. thaliana*

In *A. thaliana*, β -sitosterol, campesterol, stigmasterol, sitostanol, brassicasterol, cholesterol and, after treatment with some compounds, also 14 α ,24¹-dimethylfecosterol and 14 α -methyl-24(24¹)-dihydrofecosterol could be detected and quantified by GC-MS.

Like in cress, the bulk sterol composition was only slightly effected by (-)-BRZ1 although some changes appeared significant. For instance, β -sitosterol (p 0.01, 0.001 for 1x and 3x treated plant respectively), campesterol (0.001, <0.001) and cholesterol (p value is 0.008 for 3x treated plant only) showed slightly altered contents. On the other hand, this enantiomer did not show any effect on the

stigmasterol content and showed very little effect on the brassicasterol content. Importantly, $14\alpha,24^1$ -dimethylfecosterol and 14α -methyl- $24(24^1)$ -dihydrofecosterol could not be detected, indicating that (-)-BRZ1 does not inhibit the activity of CYP51.

Similar to (-)-BRZ1 also (+)-BRZ1 had a small yet in some cases significant effect on the sterol composition. Again, no $14\alpha,24^1$ -dimethylfecosterol and 14α -methyl- $24(24^1)$ -dihydrofecosterol was detected showing that (+)-BRZ1 does not inhibit CYP51.

In contrast, (-)-BRZ2 and (+)-BRZ2 had a strong impact on the sterol composition except for cholesterol. Also 14α -methylmethyl- $24(24^1)$ -dihydrofecosterol and $14\alpha,24^1$ -dimethylfecosterol were detected indicating that the BRZ2 enantiomers inhibit CYP51.

In summary, the sterol analyses show that the most active enantiomer (-)-BRZ1 has no relevant impact on sterol composition while both BRZ2 enantiomers seem to inhibit CYP51 to some extent. The results for *A. thaliana* are in good agreement with that obtained with *cress*.

A.

B.

C.

D.

Figure 32: Sterol composition in BRZ treated *A. thaliana* plants. Plants were grown in 21°C under long-day conditions (16 h light at 80 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ and 8 h dark) for 14 days. **(A)** Content of β -sitosterol in (-)-BRZ1, (+)-BRZ1, (-)-BRZ2 and (+)-BRZ2 treated 2 weeks old *A. thaliana* plants treated with 1x and 3x of IC₅₀; **(B)** campesterol content in 2 weeks old *A. thaliana* plants treated with 1x and 3x of IC₅₀ of (-)-BRZ1, (+)-BRZ1, (-)-BRZ2 and (+)-BRZ2; **(C)** stigmasterol content in (-)-BRZ1, (+)-BRZ1, (-)-BRZ2 and (+)-BRZ2 treated 2 weeks old *A. thaliana* plants treated with 1x and 3x of IC₅₀; **(D)** brassicasterol content in 2 weeks old *A. thaliana* plants treated with 1x and 3x of IC₅₀ of (-)-BRZ1, (+)-BRZ1, (-)-BRZ2 and (+)-BRZ2; **(E)** sitostanol content in 2 weeks old *A. thaliana* plants treated with 1x and 3x of IC₅₀ of (-)-BRZ1, (+)-BRZ1, (-)-BRZ2 and (+)-BRZ2; **(F)** cholesterol content in 2 weeks old *A. thaliana* plants treated with 1x and 3x of IC₅₀ of (-)-BRZ1, (+)-BRZ1, (-)-BRZ2 and (+)-BRZ2; **(G)** 14 α -Methyl-24(24¹)-dihydrofocosterol content in 2 weeks old *A. thaliana* plants treated with 1x and 3x of IC₅₀ of (-)-BRZ1, (+)-BRZ1, (-)-BRZ2 and (+)-BRZ2; **(H)** 14 α ,24¹-dimethylfocosterol content in 2 weeks old *A. thaliana* plants treated with 1x and 3x of IC₅₀ of (-)-BRZ1, (+)-BRZ1, (-)-BRZ2 and (+)-BRZ2. Note: Control represents the plant treated with DMSO. The Error bar represents the SD for all figures.

4. Discussion

Brassinosteroids are important plant steroid hormones involved in regulation of many aspects of plant growth and development including cell elongation and differentiation, pollen tube growth, seed yield and stress resistance (Clouse, 2011a). Brassinazole (BRZ) is the most frequently used inhibitor for brassinosteroid biosynthesis in research. So far, BRZ has been applied in more than 1000 studies. In spite of its importance, little is known about its stereo-chemical activity relationship and so far it has been used as a mixture of the stereoisomers.

In the study presented here BRZ was synthesised via a three-step protocol adapted from (Min *et al.*, 1999). Investigation by HPLC and NMR revealed that the diastereomers named (\pm)-BRZ1 and (\pm)-BRZ2 were formed with highly different efficiencies with (\pm)-BRZ1 being the main product. (\pm)-BRZ1 could be purified by recrystallisation while (\pm)-BRZ2 was isolated from the mother liquor of (\pm)-BRZ1 recrystallisation by preparative HPLC using a Luna C18(2) column. Identity of the products, (\pm)-BRZ1 and (\pm)-BRZ2, was confirmed by CHN analysis, quantification of the chlorine content, IR and NMR spectroscopy. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectroscopy analysis performed by Dr. Oliver Frank at the chair of Prof. Hoffman, Food Chemistry and Molecular Sensory Science, Technical University of Munich showed that the observed shift of the methyl group of the main product (\pm)-BRZ1 was 1.29 ppm while the same group of the by-product (\pm)-BRZ2 showed a shift of 1.63 ppm. Previously, it was shown that the shifts of the α -methyl group of compounds similar to brassinazole show chemical proton shifts in the range of 1.23 - 1.38 ppm for *RS/SR* and of 1.52 - 1.74 ppm for *RR/SS* enantiomers (Buschmann *et al.*, 1986). This suggests that (-)-BRZ1 is the racemic mixture of the (*2R,3S*) and (*2S,3R*) stereoisomers while (\pm)-BRZ2 is the racemate of the (*2R,3R*) and (*2S,3S*) stereoisomers.

Subsequently, the racemic mixtures were separated into the enantiomers (-)-BRZ1 and (+)-BRZ1 for the major product and (-)-BRZ2 and (+)-BRZ2 for the by-product by semi-preparative HPLC using a Chiralpak AD column. Using the pure compounds optical activities were measured by ORD and CD spectroscopy, which allowed assigning the signs. The ORD spectroscopy results confirmed that (-)-BRZ1 and (+)-BRZ1 as well as (-)-BZR1 and (+)-BRZ2 are enantiomers. In order to identify the absolute configuration CD spectra were measured and compared with CD spectra calculated using the density functional theory (DFT). DFT calculations were carried out by Sarah Schmitz at the chair of Prof. Grimme, Department of Theoretical Chemistry, University of Bonn, Germany. However, CD spectra prediction by different DFT methods revealed contrasting results and thus assignment of the absolute configuration failed (Figure 26).

The biological activities of the four stereoisomers were assessed, according to previous studies (Sekimata *et al.*, 2002a), using cress (*Lepidium sativum*) and *A. thaliana* Columbia-0 (Col-0). Cress hypocotyl elongation assays are widely used for determining the potency of plant hormone biosynthesis inhibitors, particularly such targeting BR and GA biosynthesis (Min *et al.*, 1999; Sekimata *et al.*, 2001; Sekimata *et al.*, 2002a). In addition, they are also useful for determining the activity of sterol biosynthesis inhibitors (Rozhon *et al.*, 2013). In this study, hypocotyl lengths were measured and the IC_{50} values were calculated using logit regression. The inhibitory activities for cress and *Arabidopsis* are listed in Table 13 and Table 14, expressed by IC_{50} values. The IC_{50} results elucidated

that (-)-BRZ1 has the highest inhibitory activity followed by (-)-BRZ2. (+)-BRZ1 and (+)-BRZ2 showed only weak activity in hypocotyl elongation assays.

Sekimata and his group presented the stereochemical structure-activity relationship of Brz220 using *A. thaliana* hypocotyl elongation assays (Sekimata *et al.*, 2008) and Oh *et al.*, (2013) reported the stereochemical structure-activity relationship of YCZ-2013. These two previously reported data of Brz220 and YCZ-2013 are shown in Table 15 as a reference for discussion. The IC₅₀ value of the four stereoisomer of YCZ-2013 ranges from 0.02 - 3.9 μ M and for the IC₅₀ value of BRZ ranges from 0.05 - 1.10 μ M, while the stereoisomers of Brz220 range from 1.21 - 18.7 μ M. This result implied that the inhibitory potency of YCZ-2013 and BRZ are higher than Brz220. The rate of the IC₅₀ value of the active form of YCZ-2013 is 50 times higher and BRZ is 22 times higher than Brz220, which could be an agreement with a previous study when using an epimeric mixture (Yamada *et al.*, 2013; Oh *et al.*, 2013).

Table 15: IC₅₀ values obtained from *A. thaliana* hypocotyl growth

Compounds	IC ₅₀ (μ M)	Compounds	IC ₅₀ (μ M)	Compounds	IC ₅₀ (μ M)
(-)-BRZ1	0.053	(2 <i>S</i> ,4 <i>R</i>)-YCZ-2013	0.024±0.003	(2 <i>S</i> ,4 <i>R</i>)-Brz220	1.21
(+)-BRZ1	0.728	(2 <i>R</i> ,4 <i>S</i>)-YCZ-2013	0.024±0.002	(2 <i>R</i> ,4 <i>S</i>)-Brz220	6.95
(-)-BRZ2	0.178	(2 <i>S</i> ,4 <i>S</i>)-YCZ-2013	1.51±0.05	(2 <i>S</i> ,4 <i>S</i>)-Brz220	2.33
(+)-BRZ2	1.106	(2 <i>R</i> ,4 <i>R</i>)-YCZ-2013	3.9±0.332	(2 <i>R</i> ,4 <i>R</i>)-Brz220	18.7

Note: Data for YCZ-2013 are adopted from Oh *et al.*, 2013 and data for Brz220 are adopted from Yamada *et al.*, 2013 and

Since many triazoles also have an impact on sterol biosynthesis, GC-MS analysis was used to quantify the sterol composition of cress and *A. thaliana* treated with the synthesised compounds. Plants were treated with 1x and 3x of IC₅₀ concentration of the BRZ enantiomers. Control plants were treated with DMSO as negative control and (for cress) with voriconazole as a positive control for inhibiting sterol biosynthesis. The GC-MS results showed that the most active enantiomer, (-)-BRZ1, had minor impact on sterol biosynthesis. Also the other enantiomer, (+)-BRZ1, had minor impact on sterol composition. In contrast, the two BRZ2 enantiomers inhibited sterol biosynthesis as indicated by appearance of unusual sterols including 14 α -methylfecosterol, 24(24¹)-dihydrofecosterol and 14 α , 24¹-dimethylfecosterol. The appearance of those unusual sterols has recently been reported for *Arabidopsis* plants treated with voriconazole, an inhibitor of sterol biosynthesis (Rozhon *et al.*, 2013). In conclusion, the bioassays revealed that (-)-BRZ1 shows the highest inhibitory activity among all stereoisomer. This enantiomer does not inhibit sterol biosynthesis, indicating that it is specific for BR biosynthesis. On the other hand, the remaining stereoisomers exhibited lower inhibitory activity and two of them also inhibited sterol biosynthesis, an undesired side effect for a BR biosynthesis inhibitor. Thus, preferentially (-)-BRZ1 should be used for inhibition of BR biosynthesis to achieve highest activity at minimal side effects.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: CHN analysis and chlorine content of P2

Element	Measured % (w/w)	Expected % (w/w)
C	65.49	65.65
H	4.53	4.61
N	13.48	13.53
Cl	11.37	11.48

Note: 2 replicates were performed for CHN analysis and 3 replicates were performed for chlorine content

Appendix 2: Preparation of (±)-BRZ1 stock solutions of the inhibitor for cress or *A. thaliana*

- 1) 100 mM stock was prepared from (±)-BRZ1 with DMSO
- 2) To prepare a 30 mM stock, mixed 30 µl of the 100 mM stock with 70 µl DMSO.
- 3) To prepare a 10 mM stock, mixed 10 µl of the 100 mM stock with 90 µl DMSO.
- 4) To prepare a 3 mM stock, mixed 30 µl of the 100 mM stock with 970 µl DMSO.
- 5) To prepare a 1 mM stock, mixed 10 µl of the 100 mM stock with 990 µl DMSO.
- 6) To prepare a 0.3 mM stock, mixed 10 µl of the 30 mM stock with 90 µl DMSO.
- 7) To prepare a 0.1 mM stock, mixed 10 µl of the 10 mM stock with 90 µl DMSO.
- 8) To prepare a 0.03 mM stock, mixed 10 µl of the 30 mM stock with 990 µl DMSO.
- 9) To prepare a 0.01 mM stock, mixed 10 µl of the 10 mM stock with 990 µl DMSO.

Appendix 3: Preparation of (-)-BRZ1 stock solutions of the inhibitor for cress or *A. thaliana*

- 1) 163.9 mM (-)-BRZ1 stock received from Dr. Rozon
- 2) To prepare a 30 mM stock, mixed 18.3 µl of the 163.9 mM (-)-BRZ1 with 81.7 µl DMSO.
- 3) To prepare a 10 mM stock, mixed 6.10 µl of the 163.9 mM (-)-BRZ1 with 93.9 µl DMSO.
- 4) To prepare a 3 mM stock, mixed 10 µl of the 30 mM (-)-BRZ1 with 90 µl DMSO.
- 5) To prepare a 1 mM stock, mixed 10 µl of the 10 mM (-)-BRZ1 with 90 µl DMSO.
- 6) To prepare a 0.3 mM stock, mixed 10 µl of the 3 mM (-)-BRZ1 with 90 µl DMSO.
- 7) To prepare a 0.1 mM stock, mixed 10 µl of the 1 mM (-)-BRZ1 with 90 µl DMSO.
- 8) To prepare a 0.03 mM stock, mixed 10 µl of the 0.3 mM (-)-BRZ1 with 90 µl DMSO.
- 9) To prepare a 0.01 mM stock, mixed 10 µl of the 0.1 mM (-)-BRZ1 with 90 µl DMSO

Appendix 4: Preparation of (+)-BRZ1 stock solutions of the inhibitor for cress or *A. thaliana*

- 1) 160.1 mM (+)-BRZ1 stock received from Dr. Rozon
- 2) To prepare a 30 mM stock, mixed 18.7 µl of the 160.1 mM (+)-BRZ1 with 81.7 µl DMSO.
- 3) To prepare a 10 mM stock, mixed 6.22 µl of the 160.1 mM (+)-BRZ1 with 93.9 µl DMSO.
- 4) To prepare a 3 mM stock, mixed 10 µl of the 30 mM (+)-BRZ1 with 90 µl DMSO.
- 5) To prepare a 1 mM stock, mixed 10 µl of the 10 mM (+)-BRZ1 with 90 µl DMSO.
- 6) To prepare a 0.3 mM stock, mixed 10 µl of the 3 mM (+)-BRZ1 with 90 µl DMSO.
- 7) To prepare a 0.1 mM stock, mixed 10 µl of the 1 mM (+)-BRZ1 with 90 µl DMSO.
- 8) To prepare a 0.03 mM stock, mixed 10 µl of the 0.3 mM (+)-BRZ1 with 90 µl DMSO.
- 9) To prepare a 0.01 mM stock, mixed 10 µl of the 0.1 mM (+)-BRZ1 with 90 µl DMSO.

Appendix 5: Preparation of (±)-BRZ2 stock solutions of the inhibitor for cress or *A. thaliana*

- 1) 100 mM stock was prepared from (±)-BRZ2 with DMSO
- 2) To prepare a 30 mM stock, mixed 30 µl of the 100 mM stock with 70 µl DMSO.
- 3) To prepare a 10 mM stock, mixed 10 µl of the 100 mM stock with 90 µl DMSO.
- 4) To prepare a 3 mM stock, mixed 30 µl of the 100 mM stock with 970 µl DMSO.
- 5) To prepare a 1 mM stock, mixed 10 µl of the 100 mM stock with 990 µl DMSO.
- 6) To prepare a 0.3 mM stock, mixed 10 µl of the 30 mM stock with 90 µl DMSO.
- 7) To prepare a 0.1 mM stock, mixed 10 µl of the 10 mM stock with 90 µl DMSO.
- 8) To prepare a 0.03 mM stock, mixed 10 µl of the 30 mM stock with 990 µl DMSO.
- 9) To prepare a 0.01 mM stock, mixed 10 µl of the 10 mM stock with 990 µl DMSO.

Appendix 6: Preparation of (-)-BRZ2 stock solutions of the inhibitor for cress or *A. thaliana*

- 1) 100 mM (-)-BRZ2 stock received from Dr. Rozon
- 2) To prepare a 30 mM stock, mixed 30 µl of the 100 mM stock with 70 µl DMSO.
- 3) To prepare a 10 mM stock, mixed 10 µl of the 100 mM stock with 90 µl DMSO.
- 4) To prepare a 3 mM stock, mixed 10 µl of the 30 mM stock with 90 µl DMSO.
- 5) To prepare a 1 mM stock, mixed 10 µl of the 10 mM stock with 90 µl DMSO.
- 6) To prepare a 0.3 mM stock, mixed 10 µl of the 3 mM stock with 90 µl DMSO.
- 7) To prepare a 0.1 mM stock, mixed 10 µl of the 1 mM stock with 90 µl DMSO.
- 8) To prepare a 0.03 mM stock, mixed 10 µl of the 0.3 mM stock with 90 µl DMSO.
- 9) To prepare a 0.01 mM stock, mixed 10 µl of the 0.1 mM stock with 90 µl DMSO.

Appendix 7: Preparation of (+)-BRZ2 stock solutions of the inhibitor for cress or *A. thaliana*

- 1) 100 mM (+)-BRZ2 stock received from Dr. Rozon
- 2) To prepare a 30 mM stock, mixed 30 µl of the 100 mM stock with 70 µl DMSO.
- 3) To prepare a 10 mM stock, mixed 10 µl of the 100 mM stock with 90 µl DMSO.
- 4) To prepare a 3 mM stock, mixed 10 µl of the 30 mM stock with 90 µl DMSO.
- 5) To prepare a 1 mM stock, mixed 10 µl of the 10 mM stock with 90 µl DMSO.
- 6) To prepare a 0.3 mM stock, mixed 10 µl of the 3 mM stock with 90 µl DMSO.
- 7) To prepare a 0.1 mM stock, mixed 10 µl of the 1 mM stock with 90 µl DMSO.
- 8) To prepare a 0.03 mM stock, mixed 10 µl of the 0.3 mM stock with 90 µl DMSO.
- 9) To prepare a 0.01 mM stock, mixed 10 µl of the 0.1 mM stock with 90 µl DMSO.

Appendix 8: Preparation of inhibitor containing media of (±)-BRZ1 for cress

Jar No.	Stock solution	Final concentration in the medium
1	5 µl of DMSO	0 µM
2	5 µl of 0.01 mM of stock	0.001 µM
3	5 µl of 0.03 mM of stock	0.003 µM
4	5 µl of 0.1 mM of stock	0.01 µM
5	5 µl of 0.3 mM of stock	0.03 µM
6	5 µl of 1 mM of stock	0.1 µM
7	5 µl of 3 mM of stock	0.3 µM
8	5 µl of 10 mM of stock	1 µM
9	5 µl of 30 mM of stock	3 µM
10	5 µl of 100 mM of stock	10 µM
11	15 µl of 100 mM of stock	30 µM
12	50 µl of 100 mM of stock	100 µM

Note: 50 ml ½ MS medium used for all jars.

Appendix 9: Preparation of inhibitor containing media of (-)-BRZ1 for cress

Jar No.	Stock solution	Final concentration in the medium
1	5 µl of DMSO	0 µM
2	5 µl of 0.01 mM (-)-BRZ1	0.001 µM
3	5 µl of 0.03 mM (-)-BRZ1	0.003 µM
4	5 µl of 0.1 mM (-)-BRZ1	0.01 µM
5	5 µl of 0.3 mM (-)-BRZ1	0.03 µM
6	5 µl of 1 mM (-)-BRZ1	0.1 µM
7	5 µl of 3 mM (-)-BRZ1	0.3 µM
8	5 µl of 10 mM (-)-BRZ1	1 µM
9	5 µl of 30 mM (-)-BRZ1	3 µM
10	3.05 µl of 163.9 mM (-)-BRZ1	10 µM
11	9.15 µl of 163.9 mM (-)-BRZ1	30 µM

Note: 25 ml liquid ½ MS medium used for jar no 10 and 11. For rest of the jars used 50 liquid ½ MS medium

Appendix 10: Preparation of inhibitor containing media of (+)-BRZ1 for cress

Jar No.	Stock solution	Final concentration in the medium
1	5 µl of DMSO	0 µM
2	5 µl of 0.01 mM (+)-BRZ1	0.001 µM
3	5 µl of 0.03 mM (+)-BRZ1	0.003 µM
4	5 µl of 0.1 mM (+)-BRZ1	0.01 µM
5	5 µl of 0.3 mM (+)-BRZ1	0.03 µM
6	5 µl of 1 mM (+)-BRZ1	0.1 µM
7	5 µl of 3 mM (+)-BRZ1	0.3 µM
8	5 µl of 10 mM (+)-BRZ1	1 µM
9	5 µl of 30 mM (+)-BRZ1	3 µM
10	1.56 µl of 160.1 mM (+)-BRZ1	10 µM
11	4.67 µl of 160.1 mM (+)-BRZ1	30 µM
12	15.6 µl of 160.1 mM (+)-BRZ1	100 µM

Note: 25 ml liquid ½ MS medium used for Jar no 10, 11 and 12. For rest of the jars used 50 liquid ½ MS medium

Appendix 11: Preparation of inhibitor containing media of (±)-BRZ2 for cress

Jar No.	Stock solution	Final concentration in the medium
1	5 µl of DMSO	0 µM
2	5 µl of 0.01 mM of stock	0.001 µM
3	5 µl of 0.03 mM of stock	0.003 µM
4	5 µl of 0.1 mM of stock	0.01 µM
5	5 µl of 0.3 mM of stock	0.03 µM
6	5 µl of 1 mM of stock	0.1 µM
7	5 µl of 3 mM of stock	0.3 µM
8	5 µl of 10 mM of stock	1 µM
9	5 µl of 30 mM of stock	3 µM
10	5 µl of 100 mM of stock	10 µM
11	15 µl of 100 mM of stock	30 µM
12	50 µl of 100 mM of stock	100 µM

Appendix 12: Preparation of inhibitor containing media of (-)-BRZ2 for cress

Jar No.	Stock solution	Final concentration in the medium
1	5 μ l of DMSO	0 μ M
2	5 μ l of 0.01 mM of stock	0.001 μ M
3	5 μ l of 0.03 mM of stock	0.003 μ M
4	5 μ l of 0.1 mM of stock	0.01 μ M
5	5 μ l of 0.3 mM of stock	0.03 μ M
6	5 μ l of 1 mM of stock	0.1 μ M
7	5 μ l of 3 mM of stock	0.3 μ M
8	5 μ l of 10 mM of stock	1 μ M
9	5 μ l of 30 mM of stock	3 μ M
10	5 μ l of 100 mM of stock	10 μ M
11	15 μ l of 100 mM of stock	30 μ M
12	50 μ l of 100 mM of stock	100 μ M

Appendix 13: Preparation of inhibitor containing media of (+)-BRZ2 for cress

Jar No.	Stock solution of (+)-BRZ2	Final concentration in the medium
1	5 μ l of DMSO	0 μ M
2	5 μ l of 0.01 mM of stock	0.001 μ M
3	5 μ l of 0.03 mM of stock	0.003 μ M
4	5 μ l of 0.1 mM of stock	0.01 μ M
5	5 μ l of 0.3 mM of stock	0.03 μ M
6	5 μ l of 1 mM of stock	0.1 μ M
7	5 μ l of 3 mM of stock	0.3 μ M
8	5 μ l of 10 mM of stock	1 μ M
9	5 μ l of 30 mM of stock	3 μ M
10	5 μ l of 100 mM of stock	10 μ M
11	15 μ l of 100 mM of stock	30 μ M
12	50 μ l of 100 mM of stock	100 μ M

Appendix 14: Preparation of inhibitor stock solution (\pm)-BRZ1 for *A. thaliana*

Petri dish	Stock solution of (\pm)-BRZ1	Final concentration in the medium
1	1 μ l of DMSO	0 μ M
2	1 μ l of 0.01 mM of stock	0.001 μ M
3	1 μ l of 0.03 mM of stock	0.003 μ M
4	1 μ l of 0.1 mM of stock	0.01 μ M
5	1 μ l of 0.3 mM of stock	0.03 μ M
6	1 μ l of 1 mM of stock	0.1 μ M
7	1 μ l of 3 mM of stock	0.3 μ M
8	1 μ l of 10 mM of stock	1 μ M
9	1 μ l of 30 mM of stock	3 μ M
10	1 μ l of 100 mM of stock	10 μ M
11	3 μ l of 100 mM of stock	30 μ M
12	10 μ l of 100 mM of stock	100 μ M

Note: 10 ml liquid $\frac{1}{2}$ MS medium used for each petri dish

Appendix 15: Preparation of inhibitor stock solution (-)-BRZ1 for *A. thaliana*

Petri dish	Stock solution of (-)-BRZ1	Final concentration in the medium
1	1 µl of DMSO	0 µM
2	1 µl of 0.01 mM of (-)-BRZ1 stock	0.001 µM
3	1 µl of 0.03 mM of (-)-BRZ1 stock	0.003 µM
4	1 µl of 0.1 mM of (-)-BRZ1 stock	0.01 µM
5	1 µl of 0.3 mM of (-)-BRZ1 stock	0.03 µM
6	1 µl of 1 mM of (-)-BRZ1 stock	0.1 µM
7	1 µl of 3 mM of (-)-BRZ1 stock	0.3 µM
8	1 µl of 10 mM of (-)-BRZ1 stock	1 µM
9	1 µl of 30 mM of (-)-BRZ1 stock	3 µM
10	0.61 µl of 163.9 mM of (-)-BRZ1 stock	10 µM
11	1.83 µl of 163.9 mM of (-)-BRZ1 stock	30 µM

Note: 10 ml liquid ½ MS medium used for each petri dish

Appendix 16: Preparation of inhibitor stock solution (+)-BRZ1 for *A. thaliana*

Petri dish	Stock solution of (+)-BRZ1	Final concentration in the medium
1	1 µl of DMSO	0 µM
2	1 µl of 0.01 mM of (+)-BRZ1 stock	0.001 µM
3	1 µl of 0.03 mM of (+)-BRZ1 stock	0.003 µM
4	1 µl of 0.1 mM of (+)-BRZ1 stock	0.01 µM
5	1 µl of 0.3 mM of (+)-BRZ1 stock	0.03 µM
6	1 µl of 1 mM of (+)-BRZ1 stock	0.1 µM
7	1 µl of 3 mM of (+)-BRZ1 stock	0.3 µM
8	1 µl of 10 mM of (+)-BRZ1 stock	1 µM
9	1 µl of 30 mM of (+)-BRZ1 stock	3 µM
10	0.62 µl of 160.1 mM of (+)-BRZ1 stock	10 µM
11	1.87 µl of 160.1 mM of (+)-BRZ1 stock	30 µM
12	6.24 µl of 160.1 mM of (+)-BRZ1 stock	100 µM

Note: 10 ml liquid ½ MS medium used for each petri dish

Appendix 17: Preparation of inhibitor stock solution (±)-BRZ2 for *A. thaliana*

Petri dish	Stock solution of (±)-BRZ2	Final concentration in the medium
1	1 µl of DMSO	0 µM
2	1 µl of 0.01 mM of stock	0.001 µM
3	1 µl of 0.03 mM of stock	0.003 µM
4	1 µl of 0.1 mM of stock	0.01 µM
5	1 µl of 0.3 mM of stock	0.03 µM
6	1 µl of 1 mM of stock	0.1 µM
7	1 µl of 3 mM of stock	0.3 µM
8	1 µl of 10 mM of stock	1 µM
9	1 µl of 30 mM of stock	3 µM
10	1 µl of 100 mM of stock	10 µM
11	3 µl of 100 mM of stock	30 µM
12	10 µl of 100 mM of stock	100 µM

Note: 10 ml liquid ½ MS medium used for each petri dish

Appendix 18: Preparation of inhibitor stock solution (-)-BRZ2 for *A. thaliana*

Petri dish	Stock solution of (-)-BRZ2	Final concentration in the medium
1	1 µl of DMSO	0 µM
2	1 µl of 0.01 mM of stock	0.001 µM
3	1 µl of 0.03 mM of stock	0.003 µM
4	1 µl of 0.1 mM of stock	0.01 µM
5	1 µl of 0.3 mM of stock	0.03 µM
6	1 µl of 1 mM of stock	0.1 µM
7	1 µl of 3 mM of stock	0.3 µM
8	1 µl of 10 mM of stock	1 µM
9	1 µl of 30 mM of stock	3 µM
10	0.62 µl of 160.1 mM stock	10 µM
11	1.87 µl of 160.1 mM of stock	30 µM
12	6.24 µl of 160.1 mM of stock	100 µM

Note: 10 ml liquid ½ MS medium used for each petri dish

Appendix 19: Preparation of inhibitor stock solution (+)-BRZ2 for *A. thaliana*

Petri dish	Stock solution of (+)-BRZ2	Final concentration in the medium
1	1 µl of DMSO	0 µM
2	1 µl of 0.01 mM of stock	0.001 µM
3	1 µl of 0.03 mM of stock	0.003 µM
4	1 µl of 0.1 mM of stock	0.01 µM
5	1 µl of 0.3 mM of stock	0.03 µM
6	1 µl of 1 mM of stock	0.1 µM
7	1 µl of 3 mM of stock	0.3 µM
8	1 µl of 10 mM of stock	1 µM
9	1 µl of 30 mM of stock	3 µM
10	0.62 µl of 160.1 mM stock	10 µM
11	1.87 µl of 160.1 mM of stock	30 µM
12	6.24 µl of 160.1 mM of stock	100 µM

Note: 10 ml liquid ½ MS medium used for each petri dish

Appendix 20: Preparation of the stock solution for western analysis of *A. thaliana*

Compound	Stock solution mM	Final concentration in the medium (µM)
DMSO	5 µl of DMSO	0
(-)-BRZ1	5 µl of 1 mM stock	0.5
(-)-BRZ1	3.3 µl of 3 mM stock	1
(+)-BRZ1	5 µl of 1 mM stock	0.5
(+)-BRZ1	3.33 µl of 3 mM stock	1
(-)-BRZ2	5 µl of 1 mM stock	0.5
(-)-BRZ2	3.33 µl of 3 mM stock	1
(+)-BRZ2	5 µl of 1 mM stock	0.5
(+)-BRZ2	3.33 µl of 3 mM stock	1

Appendix 21: Preparation of the stock solution for GC-MS analysis using cress IC₅₀X1 and IC₅₀X3 values

Compound	Final concentration in the medium (µM)	Stock solution mM
DMSO	0	5 µl of DMSO
(-)-BRZ1 IC ₅₀ X1	0.233	5 µl of 2.33 mM stock
(-)-BRZ1 IC ₅₀ X3	0.699	5 µl of 6.99 mM stock
(+)-BRZ1 IC ₅₀ X1	2.703	5 µl of 27.03 mM stock
(+)-BRZ1 IC ₅₀ X3	8.109	5 µl of 81.09 mM stock
(-)-BRZ2 IC ₅₀ X1	0.890	5 µl of 8.9 mM stock
(-)-BRZ2 IC ₅₀ X3	2.670	5 µl of 26.7 mM stock
(+)-BRZ2 IC ₅₀ X1	2.822	5 µl of 28.22 mM stock
(+)-BRZ2 IC ₅₀ X3	8.466	5 µl of 84.66 mM stock
Voriconazole IC ₅₀ X1	0.077	5 µl of 0.77 mM stock
Voriconazole IC ₅₀ X3	0.233	5 µl of 2.33 mM stock

Note: 50 ml ½ MS liquid medium along with inhibitor containing media used for each stock solution. The IC₅₀X1 and IC₅₀X3 values of voriconazole were taken from the study carried by previous master student Robert Vassallo and Natalie Kraus.

Appendix 22: Preparation of the stock solution for GC-MS analysis using *A. thaliana* IC₅₀X1 and IC₅₀X3 values

Compound	Final concentration in the medium (µM)	Stock solution mM
DMSO	0	5 µl of DMSO
(-)-BRZ1 IC ₅₀ X1	0.053	0.53 µl of 1 mM stock
(-)-BRZ1 IC ₅₀ X3	0.159	1.6 µl of 1 mM stock
(+)-BRZ1 IC ₅₀ X1	0.728	2.43 µl of 3 mM stock
(+)-BRZ1 IC ₅₀ X3	2.184	7.3 µl of 3 mM stock
(-)-BRZ2 IC ₅₀ X1	0.178	1.78 µl of 1 mM stock
(-)-BRZ2 IC ₅₀ X3	0.534	5.3 µl of 1 mM stock
(+)-BRZ2 IC ₅₀ X1	1.106	3.69 µl of 3 mM stock
(+)-BRZ2 IC ₅₀ X3	3.318	11.1 µl of 3 mM stock

Note: 10 ml ½ MS liquid medium along with inhibitor containing media used for each stock solution.

Appendix 23: IR spectrum of 1-phenyl-2-(1H-1,2,4-triazole-1-yl)ethanone (P1)

Appendix 24: IR spectra measurement of 3-(4-chlorophenyl)-1-phenyl-2-(1*H*-1,2,4-triazol-1-yl)propan-1-one (P2).

Appendix 25: Cress hypocotyls length treated with (-)-BRZ1

Figure 33: The relationship between cress hypocotyls length (in cm) and different concentrations (in $\mu\text{mol/l}$) of (-)-BRZ1 (experiment 1 and experiment 3)

Appendix 26: Cress hypocotyls length treated with (+)-BRZ1

Figure 34: The relationship between cress hypocotyls length (in cm) and different concentrations (in $\mu\text{mol/l}$) of (+)-BRZ1 (experiment 1 and experiment 2)

Appendix 27: Cress hypocotyls length treated with (-)-BRZ2

Figure 35: The relationship between cress hypocotyls length (in cm) and different concentrations (in μmol/l) of (-)-BRZ2 (experiment 1 and experiment 3)

Appendix 28: Cress hypocotyls length treated with (+)-BRZ2

Figure 36: The relationship between cress hypocotyls length (in cm) and different concentrations (in μmol/l) of (+)-BRZ2 (experiment 2 and experiment 3)

Appendix 29: Cress hypocotyls length treated with (±)-BRZ1

Figure 37: The relationship between cress hypocotyls length (in cm) and different concentrations (in μmol/l) of (±)-BRZ1 (experiment 2 and experiment 3)

Appendix 30: Cress hypocotyls length treated with (\pm)-BRZ2

Figure 38: The relationship between cress hypocotyls length (in cm) and different concentrations (in $\mu\text{mol/l}$) of (\pm)-BRZ2 (experiment 2 and experiment 3)

Appendix 31: *A. thaliana* hypocotyls length treated with (-)-BRZ1

Figure 39: The relationship between *A. thaliana* hypocotyls length (in mm) and different concentrations (in $\mu\text{mol/l}$) of (-)-BRZ1 (experiment 1 and experiment 3)

Appendix 32: *A. thaliana* hypocotyls length treated with (+)-BRZ1

Figure 40: The relationship between *A. thaliana* hypocotyls length (in mm) and different concentrations (in $\mu\text{mol/l}$) of (+)-BRZ1 (experiment 1 and experiment 2)

Appendix 33: *A. thaliana* hypocotyls length treated with (-)-BRZ2

Figure 41: The relationship between *A. thaliana* hypocotyls length (in mm) and different concentrations (in μmol/l) of (-)-BRZ2 (experiment 2 and experiment 3)

Appendix 34: *A. thaliana* hypocotyls length treated with (+)-BRZ2

Figure 42: The relationship between *A. thaliana* hypocotyls length (in mm) and different concentrations (in μmol/l) of (+)-BRZ2 (experiment 2 and experiment 3)